

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Ex-post assessment of the solution reports (LCA)

Deliverable 5.7

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the ex-post assessment of climate adaptation solutions implemented across six TransformAr demonstrators, using and advancing the Sustainability Rating Method (SRM) as a framework for evaluating resilience capacity. While grounded in applied analysis, D5.7 also functions as a methodological guide, illustrating how SRM and its indicator system can be adapted for real-world use. Unlike traditional evaluations, this deliverable is designed to support both outcome interpretation and future assessment design across diverse operational contexts.

It contributes to the objectives of WP5 (Accelerating demonstrators' transformational adaptation) by supporting the validation and transfer of tested solutions, offering structured tools and reflections to strengthen long-term implementation, replication, and scaling. D5.7 builds on the methodological foundations developed in D5.2 (sustainability profiles) and D5.9 (SRM tool) and bridges them with forward-looking indicators of resilience.

The methodology emphasizes the design of assessment frameworks by grounding them in a strong theoretical foundation and providing practical approaches for implementation. It integrates multiple layers of evidence collection through triangulation, including the co-development of indicators with Demonstrators and Technical Support Partners (TSPs) using semi-structured interviews conducted via Participatory Insights Modules (PIM). To ensure methodological consistency and data efficiency, the same indicators are applied in the resilience assessment, scored across three dimensions—Relevance, Confidence, and Timespan—to capture both achieved results and anticipated future performance. The analysis covers 18 validated solutions across five Actionable Adaptation Solution (AAS) types: Behavioural Change and Awareness-Raising (BCAR), Governance Schemes (GS), Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), Technological and Digital Solutions (TDS), and Insurance, Financial and Economic Instruments (IFE).

Key findings include the critical role of solution portfolios. For example, in Lappeenranta, environmental (URB), monitoring (SWMM), and civic engagement (CAF) solutions work as a coordinated system to address urban water and resilience challenges. Solutions that combine physical interventions, data infrastructure, and community participation demonstrated higher resilience capacity than stand-alone approaches. Across all solutions, the Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation category was the most applied, reflecting its importance for adaptive management. Physical risk domains such as Flood Vulnerability and Data Quality achieved the highest scores in both Relevance and Confidence, confirming the credibility of data-driven approaches. Solutions with short Timespans performed well in Relevance but showed lower Confidence, reflecting uncertainty due to limited operational evidence or constrained resources for sustained monitoring and evaluation after the project. The results will inform final solution reports (D5.1) and region-specific guides. They also support cross-demonstrator learning and strategic planning for adaptation efforts beyond TransformAr.

This work is relevant for demonstrators, technical experts, project designers, and policymakers engaged in sustainability and resilience planning. It offers a transferable, evidence-based framework to assess adaptation interventions, link them to system-level outcomes, and design performance-based investment pathways for climate-resilient transformation.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAS	Actionable adaptive solutions
AF	Adaptation Fund
AI	Artificial intelligence
AWAR	Awareness-raising modules
BCAR	Behavioural change and awareness-raising
BNG	Biodiversity Net Gain
CAE	Citizen app Egaleo
CAF	Citizen App Finland
CEI	Choice experiment
CCA	Climate change adaptation
CC	Climate Change
CIH	Climate innovation hub
COAST	Coastal Contract
DSI	Demand analysis for social services and infrastructures
GB	Green bonds
GS	Governance schemes
HT	Handprint thinking
ICW	Integrated Constructed Wetlands
ICWM	Integrated Constructed Wetlands Monitoring
IFE	Insurance, financial and economic schemes
INTERM	Intertidal Monitoring
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KCS	Key community system
KPI	Key performance indicators
LCA	life cycle assessments
LCT	Life cycle thinking
LWO	Local Wetland Observatory
MRM	Mussel Raft Monitoring
NBS	Nature-based solution
NUDG	Nudging
PIM	Participatory Insights Module

RA	Risk assessment
RI	Resilience Index
RLL	Reflective learning loop
SCS	Smart Climate Stations
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SG	Smart gate
SRM	Sustainability rating method
SWMM	Stormwater monitoring
TDS	Technological and digital solutions
URB	Nature-based urban stormwater solution
TA	Transformational adaptation
TSP	Technical Support Partners
WP	Work Package
WRT	Westcountry Rivers Trust

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

WP5 of the TransformAr project focuses on accelerating transformational adaptation. Within this WP, Task 5.2 aims to draw insights from these demonstrations to assess how well the implemented solutions contribute to climate and social resilience. This process is documented through a set of interconnected deliverables. D5.2 introduced and tested the Sustainability Rating Method (SRM) through region-specific sustainability profiles of validated solutions. D5.9 builds upon these profiles by refining the SRM into a general methodology. This current report, D5.7, complements and connects these efforts by applying the SRM in an ex-post assessment of the solutions implemented across the six demonstrators. The goal of D5.7 is twofold: to conduct an ex-post assessment of the validated solutions implemented across the six demonstrators, and to offer methodological guidance for future users interested in integrating resilience thinking into their sustainability assessments. Figure 1.1 illustrates how these deliverables work in concert to support the TransformAr ambition of enabling scalable, evidence-based climate adaptation.

Figure 1.1 Interconnection of deliverables in Task 5.2

The SRM was originally designed to evaluate the environmental, social, and economic sustainability of Actionable adaptive solutions (AAS) across diverse regional contexts. It incorporates a structured four-phase process (Scoping, Implementation, Data Processing, and Assessment) and emphasizes linkages with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The method is rooted in Life Cycle Thinking (LCT), Handprint Thinking (HT), and a systems perspective on sustainability. In D5.2, the SRM was applied to generate detailed sustainability profiles for 19 validated solutions and six region-specific portfolios (RSPs), using both common and context-specific indicators. D5.9 built upon this foundation by operationalizing the method into an Excel-based tool, streamlining indicator selection, SDG mapping, and data visualization for users in different project stages. This digital tool facilitates the transferability of the method and supports its adaptation to evolving needs, such as pre-investment screening or regional planning. While D5.2 provided the basis for validation and interpretation, and D5.9 provided the user interface and workflow, D5.7 completes the cycle by introducing a resilience dimension, capturing how solutions perform over time, under uncertainty, and in relation to systemic climate risks. D5.7 also supports cross-demonstrator synthesis by identifying patterns across solution types and Key Community Systems (KCS), offering insights into common success factors, barriers, and emerging best practices. These findings will feed into the final refinement of the SRM and inform its wider adoption.

Ultimately, this deliverable functions not only as a results report but as a guide. It demonstrates how to carry out structured, participatory, and context-sensitive assessments of solution resilience, and how such assessments can inform investment prioritization, adaptive planning, and policy design.

1.2 Objectives and scope

D5.7 enables the structured and transferable evaluation of the sustainability and resilience capacity of TransformAr solutions by operationalizing the SRM. While D5.9 introduced the SRM as a flexible framework applicable throughout the solution lifecycle, from ex-ante design to ex-durante monitoring and ex-post reflection, D5.7 focuses on its ex-post application. At the same time, it serves as a practical guide for adapting the SRM to a variety of real-world contexts, stakeholder priorities, and operational conditions. Specifically, it:

- Demonstrates how to apply the SRM in an ex-post context to evaluate solution performance after implementation.
- Offers practical guidance on structuring life cycle-informed assessments.
- Shows how to design and refine indicators through data triangulation and stakeholder input.
- Encourages co-evaluation using Participatory Insight Modules (PIM) that link field experience to risk-based performance attributes.
- Provides a means to score solution performance along three key dimensions (relevance, confidence, and timespan) bringing foresight into resilience capacity assessment.
- Informing future replication, scaling, and policy transfer efforts through synthesis of cross demonstrator lessons.

The scope of this deliverable includes:

- Geographic coverage: six TransformAr Demonstrators, i.e., Lappeenranta (Finland), Westcountry Region (UK), Galicia (Spain), Oristano (Italy), Guadeloupe (France), and Egaleo (Greece).
- Solution types: solution types implemented in the demonstrators, across categories including Behavioural change and awareness-raising (BCAR), Governance Schemes (GS), Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), Technological and Digital Solutions (TDS), and Insurance, financial and economic schemes (IFE).
- Data sources: relevant streams informing the SRM indicators, including monitoring data, LCA results, stakeholder interviews, co-designed indicator feedback, and documentation from demonstrator teams.

D5.7 complements the SRM by illustrating how it can be applied and adapted across diverse implementation contexts. Rather than replacing the core method, this deliverable operationalizes it through real-world examples, offering accessible guidance for practitioners and decision-makers working under varying institutional and environmental conditions. In doing so, it lays the groundwork for developing solution-specific guides that can support replication in other regions. By combining outcome reporting with methodological reflection, D5.7 equips users with the tools to strengthen, scale, and transfer climate adaptation strategies using transparent and context-responsive evaluation practices.

1.3 Target audiences

D5.7 is intended for a wide range of users involved in climate adaptation, both within and beyond the TransformAr project. Its modular and practice-oriented structure is designed to accommodate varying levels of expertise, from technical experts and project managers to local stakeholders and policymakers, providing tools and insights that can be applied flexibly across diverse contexts.

Primary Audiences

- TransformAr demonstrator teams

For self-evaluation of solution impacts and lessons learned, using structured reflection across lifecycle stages and sustainability domains.

- Technical support partners (TSPs)
For guiding data collection, facilitating interviews, validating indicators, and supporting resilience scoring processes in collaboration with demonstrators.
- WP leaders and project evaluators
For integrating resilience insights into project-level learning, synthesis, and final reporting across WPs.

Secondary Audiences

- Researchers and method developers
Interested in refining or adapting the SRM and D5.7's contributions to develop improved assessment frameworks for sustainability, resilience, or other systems-level analyses.
- Solution replicators and innovation brokers
Who aim to adapt, scale, or transfer successful climate solutions to new operational settings and require structured guidance for evaluating contextual fit and readiness.
- Local and regional authorities
Seeking tested, transparent methods to assess, monitor, and replicate adaptation interventions within their planning, budgeting, or climate action frameworks.
- EU-funded project teams and consortia
Including those in Horizon Europe, LIFE, or Interreg, seeking validated tools for solution evaluation and reporting aligned with SDGs and European adaptation strategies.
- Policy and decision-makers
Interested in developing evidence-based strategies for climate adaptation and system transformation, informed by lessons from applied field experience.

2.0 METHODOLOGY DESIGN

This section outlines the methodology used to assess the sustainability of solutions across the TransformAr demonstrators, serving also as the foundation for the resilience assessment that follows. Building on the SRM introduced in Deliverable D5.9, the focus here shifts to the design and adaptation of the methodology itself—emphasizing flexibility and refinement for use across varied operational contexts, rather than prescribing a fixed set of steps.

Three components are introduced there, each aligned with the principles and structure of SRM implementation (see Figure 2.1):

- **Conceptual Foundation** – establishing the theoretical and operational principles of the assessment by integrating the three pillars (environmental, economic, and social) of sustainability with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), incorporating Societal Relations to Nature (SRN), and applying Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) and Handprint Thinking (HT) in practice;
- **Evidence Collection** – identifying and integrating multiple sources of data such as monitoring reports, modeling analyses, quantitative and qualitative insights from demonstrators and TSPs;
- **Indicator Refinement** – tailoring, adjusting and validating the original SRM indicators based on field experience, local context, and the evolving performance landscape.

Figure 2.1 Sustainability rating method implementation

While the data processing, scoring procedures and assessment are described in detail in D5.9 and D5.2, the focus of this deliverable is to guide how the assessment methodology can be designed, tailored, and improved.

2.1 Conceptual Foundation

2.1.1 Sustainability assessment framework

The sustainability assessment framework builds upon the foundational definition introduced by Brundtland Commission (Brundtland, 1987) “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. Central to this definition are the three interdependent pillars of sustainability—environmental, economic, and social—commonly illustrated using Venn diagrams, concentric circles, or structural metaphors (Giddings et al., 2002), (Lozano, 2008;

Purvis et al., 2019). These pillars serve as the ultimate endpoints of sustainable development and form the normative basis for evaluating solution performance within the TransformAr project.

Rather than seeking to reinvent existing frameworks, the assessment approach aligns with internationally recognized standards, particularly the SDGs. The SDGs are employed as midpoints—operational reference markers that provide a globally endorsed roadmap to tackle poverty, environmental degradation, and social and economic inequality (Emas, 2015; Taylor, 2016). While the SDGs offer thematic clarity and political legitimacy, their direct application at the local level may face limitations due to differences in context, priorities, and available data.

To bridge this gap and strengthen the holistic understanding of sustainability, the framework incorporates the Societal Relations to Nature (SRN) perspective as a theoretical foundation (Becker et al., 2011; Görg, 2011; Hummel et al., 2017). SRN highlights the embeddedness of societal systems within ecological processes, the dynamic interplay between human needs and environmental limits, and the co-evolution of social, economic, and ecological systems. This perspective is particularly useful for adaptation contexts, where resilience and transformation are central concerns. Drawing from Deliverable D5.2 the framework applies a structured linkage between selected SDGs, sub-goals, and performance indicators (Figure 2.2), organizing them into three domains: social (e.g., SDG1-5 & 11), economic (e.g., SDG6-10, 12, 16 & 17), and ecological (e.g., SDG13-15). These domains enable systematic and context-aware assessments of sustainability by connecting measurable impacts to globally standardized goals, while maintaining a focus on local relevance and interpretability. In doing so, the framework provides a solid foundation for evaluating adaptation solutions not only in terms of what they achieve, but how they support long-term sustainability and transformation across diverse contexts.

Figure 2.2 Sustainability assessment framework and relational entities, aspects, and assigned SDGs

2.1.2 Life cycle thinking

Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) is a foundational principle embedded within the assessment approach of TransformAr. It provides a systems-based perspective that enables project partners and stakeholders to understand entire pathway of an adaptation solution—from initial design and development through implementation, operation, and long-term impact. This holistic perspective helps identify opportunities

to improve sustainability performance at each stage of the product's life (de Fátima Maciel et al., 2024). Rather than evaluating outcomes at a single point in time, LCT encourages consideration of dynamic processes, dependencies, transitions, and trade-offs across the solution's lifespan.

The rationale for using LCT within D5.7 is threefold. First, it aligns with sustainability science best practices, where system boundaries and impact pathways are considered essential to understanding unintended consequences and long-term value. Second, LCT supports the identification of critical risks and enabling conditions that may emerge at different phases of implementation. Finally, LCT reinforces the link between sustainability and resilience by focusing not only on performance outcomes, but also on the capacity of a solution to adapt and sustain these outcomes over time.

In practice, LCT is implemented in two main ways:

1. Interview framing and reflection

Semi-structured interviews through PIM with Demonstrators and TSPs are organized around the full life cycle of the solution. Participants are prompted to reflect on key phases—such as planning and co-design, implementation, initial operation, and scaling. This approach supports the identification of phase-specific challenges (e.g., institutional barriers, cost overruns, behavioral adoption) and helps surface contextual insights not always captured in performance data.

2. Performance and indicator refinement

Drawing from these reflections, indicators used in the SRM are reassessed and refined to reflect their relevance at different life cycle stages. Each indicator is tagged to one or more life cycle phases, ensuring that the final indicator list not only evaluates outcomes, but also captures process-oriented insights related to readiness, stakeholder engagement, durability, and long-term impact. For example, an indicator measuring stakeholder participation may be relevant during early co-design, while an indicator on maintenance becomes crucial during post-deployment stages.

By integrating LCT, the D5.7 methodology ensures that the final set of indicators reflects a comprehensive, time-aware understanding of each solution's performance. This enables a deeper evaluation of both sustainability and resilience capacity, enhances the transferability of the assessment approach, and supports the development of more adaptive and future-proof solutions across TransformAr demonstrators and beyond.

2.1.3 Handprint Thinking

Handprint Thinking (HT) is used in the TransformAr assessment framework as a forward-looking and constructive complement to traditional sustainability assessment. While conventional methods often emphasize minimizing negative impacts (the "footprint"), HT shifts the focus toward maximizing positive contributions—what the solution actively improves in terms of environmental, social, and economic systems (Husgafvel, 2023). In the context of climate adaptation, this perspective is especially valuable for recognizing solutions that not only avoid harm, but also enhance resilience, equity, and well-being.

The rationale for integrating HT into D5.7 is twofold. First, it aligns with TransformAr's ambition to deliver transformative adaptation—solutions that go beyond damage control to generate systemic benefits. Second, it enables a more meaningful and stakeholder-oriented interpretation of performance indicators by emphasizing progress toward targets, not just reduction of harms. This orientation encourages engagement, supports positive storytelling, and reinforces the long-term value of adaptation investments.

In D5.7, HT is implemented in two main ways:

1. Narrative development and indicator rationale

During the indicator refinement process, Demonstrators and TSPs were encouraged to reflect on why each indicator matters—not only in measuring change, but in capturing intended positive outcomes of the solution. This includes social inclusion, ecosystem co-benefits, capacity building, and innovation spillovers. Through interviews and workshops, these narratives were documented and embedded in the indicator logic, creating a more meaningful connection between metrics and stakeholder goals.

2. Normalization using distance to target

HT also shapes how indicator scores are interpreted. Rather than only evaluating current performance in isolation, indicators are assessed based on their distance to a defined target—for example, a regulation goal, or demonstrator-defined threshold. This approach allows for normalization of indicator values that highlight how far the solution has progressed toward delivering measurable benefits. For instance, an energy savings indicator may reflect not only absolute reductions but how close the solution comes to achieving local climate neutrality objectives.

The final set of indicators in D5.7 reflects HT through clear rationale statements (explaining the positive change each indicator represents), target-based normalization (where applicable, to track contribution levels), and categorization of indicators by performance across different stages of the solution life cycle.

By embedding handprint logic into both the design and interpretation of indicators, the D5.7 methodology supports a more constructive and forward-looking assessment. It enables adaptation solutions to be recognized not only for mitigating risks, but for driving positive transformation within their communities, systems, and natural environments.

2.2 Evidence collection

Robust and context-sensitive evidence is essential for evaluating the sustainability and resilience capacity of adaptation solutions. In this deliverable, evidence collection is designed to be multi-source, multi-phase, and purpose-driven, aligning with the SRM while enabling methodological flexibility and local relevance. The goal is not only to assess whether performance targets have been met, but also to understand how, why, and under what conditions outcomes have been achieved—or constrained. This section outlines the three primary sources of evidence used in the assessment:

- Pre-identified information from the project design and planning phase (e.g. proposal Key performance indicators (KPIs), baseline deliverables);
- Monitoring and solution-specific reports, including field measurements, modelling outputs, and performance summaries;
- Semi-structured interviews through PIM, used to capture lived experience, contextual knowledge, and reflective insights from Demonstrators and TSPs.

These sources are used not in isolation, but as part of a triangulated assessment approach. They allow the methodology to integrate quantitative data (e.g., pollutions reductions), qualitative insights (e.g., stakeholder satisfaction), and participatory knowledge (e.g., outcomes from community-based innovation processes). The integration of diverse evidence types ensures a more holistic, lifecycle-informed evaluation of both sustainability impacts and resilience capacity.

2.2.1 Pre-identified information

A key foundation for the ex-post assessment methodology presented in this deliverable lies in the use of pre-identified information developed during the early design and planning phase of the TransformAr project. This phase includes the baseline documentation produced during proposal development, site scoping, and early implementation design, where KPIs, sustainability goals, and risk assumptions were first formalized. These elements serve as reference points for evaluating whether the implemented solutions have progressed as intended and how their performance aligns with original expectations.

Each TransformAr demonstrator identified a range of indicators and targets as part of its solution strategy, many of which were embedded in the project proposal and translated into demonstrator-specific work plans. This included both quantitative KPIs (e.g., reduction in pollutions, flooding events) and qualitative goals (e.g., improved institutional coordination, increased public awareness). These indicators provide the initial structure for the SRM introduced in D5.9 and tested in D5.2.

Other critical sources of pre-identified information are from the stakeholders' participation. For example, Deliverable D1.2: Stakeholder Matrix and IEs Baseline Profiles, which offered insight into each demonstrator's institutional landscape, stakeholder dynamics, and perceived climate risks. The materials also served as a basis for triangulating performance expectations during the ex-post evaluation. By comparing pre-identified indicators and targets to actual implementation data and stakeholder reflections, we are able to examine discrepancies, validate progress, and identify indicators that required adaptation or reinterpretation.

Importantly, these pre-identified elements were not treated as fixed. Rather, they provided a baseline framework upon which the methodology could evolve, particularly through the integration of local experience, observed outcomes, and contextual risk insights gathered later in the process. For example, an originally planned KPI for "become resilience" might be revised to "enhance resilience" to better reflect the continuous and adaptive nature of resilience-building. This shift emphasizes not a one-time achievement, but an ongoing process of improving the system's capacity to cope with shocks, adapt to change, and sustain performance over time. Such refinement ensures that the indicator aligns more closely with real-world conditions and evolving stakeholder expectations, particularly in complex or uncertain implementation environments.

In this way, the pre-identified information serves as both an anchor and a starting point—ensuring continuity with project objectives while supporting the adaptive development of indicators and evaluation criteria. The structured use of this early-stage information supports traceability across the solution life cycle and strengthens the reliability of performance narratives developed in D5.7.

2.2.2 Monitoring and solution-specific data

Monitoring and solution-specific reports represent a second core evidence stream. These documents capture performance data generated during the implementation phase, reflecting both the progress toward initial goals and the operational realities experienced across demonstrator sites. They provide quantitative and qualitative insights that support the verification, refinement, or reinterpretation of the pre-identified indicators introduced during the project design phase.

A central reference for this category is Deliverable D5.8 – Intermediary Monitoring Report, which includes demonstrator-level updates on KPIs, status of solution deployment, and stakeholder engagement activities. These reports contain both numeric tracking (e.g. m² of NBS implemented, number of citizens engaged, volume of water) and narrative elements summarizing barriers encountered, lessons learned, and preliminary outcomes. They serve as a crucial mid-point snapshot between initial planning and the final ex-post evaluation conducted in D5.7.

Beyond D5.8, several other forms of solution-specific documentation were reviewed:

- Field measurements and technical monitoring data (e.g., water quality testing, energy use monitoring)
- Modelling outputs, especially in cases where climate or hydrological models were used to simulate future impacts or test solution scenarios
- Experimental results from solution piloting or innovation labs

- Participatory reports produced through co-creation activities and local stakeholder workshops, often capturing qualitative shifts in awareness, trust, or governance engagement
- Cost-benefit and feasibility studies, such as those reflected in TransformAr’s “bankability” reports and business model documentation

These diverse sources offer solution-specific insights that help validate or challenge assumptions built into the original indicator set. For example, in the case of a NBS aimed at flood management, monitoring data on peak flow reduction and local ecosystem response can strengthen the evidence base for ecological and economic indicators alike. Similarly, participatory activity reports provide rich detail on process-oriented outcomes such as inclusivity, empowerment, or behavioral change—domains that are difficult to quantify but central to resilience.

Box 2.1 Monitoring and solution-specific reports from Lappeenranta, Finland

The assessment for Lappeenranta draws on a wide range of reports generated throughout TransformAr, including

- Stakeholders Matrix and IE Baseline Profiles (D1.2)
- Tools on the Avoided Damages and Benefits per Demo (D3.4)
- Replicable socio-economic impact assessment tools of transformational pathways (D3.6)
- Six Region-Specific Portfolios of Solutions (D3.8)
- Compendium of Pathways and Action Plans (D3.9)
- Intermediary Monitoring Report (D5.8)
- Learning Stories on Awareness-raising and Behavioral Change Solutions (D4.1)
- Learning Stories on Nature-Based Solutions and Book of Nature-Based Solutions (D4.3)
- Learning Stories on Digital and Technological Solution (D4.4)
- Learning Stories on Insurance and Financial Solutions (D4.5)
- Bankability reports (D5.5)

These documents support the interpretation of performance, stakeholder engagement, and adaptive capacity. While this list is not exhaustive, it reflects the diversity of sources integrated into the indicator assessment. Further methodological details are available in D5.2 – Sustainability Profiles of Solutions

Importantly, the use of monitoring reports is not limited to tracking performance outcomes. These documents also help uncover emerging risks, adaptive responses, and enabling conditions that shape the sustainability trajectory of a solution. For instance, a delay in implementation due to procurement or administrative hurdles may indicate a latent governance risk, while rapid uptake in a pilot area may suggest high social acceptance that could strengthen long-term performance.

By systematically integrating monitoring and solution-specific reporting into the evidence base, the D5.7 methodology ensures a realistic and context-aware interpretation of each solution’s performance. These insights are especially important in the indicator refinement process, where lessons from implementation are used to adjust relevance, confirm data reliability, and support the resilience scoring exercise introduced later in the deliverable.

2.2.3 Participatory Insights Module

The Participatory Insights Module (PIM) is a semi-structured, stakeholder-driven tool developed to support the SRM by capturing qualitative evidence on solution outcomes, contextual risks, and indicator

relevance. The PIM is inspired by two methods: Participatory Risk Assessment (PRA) and Outcome Harvesting (OH). PRA has been applied to facilitate stakeholder-driven identification of risks and the co-design of mitigation strategies, such as in informal food market risk assessments in sub-Saharan Africa (Grace et al., 2008), and in community-led disaster preparedness initiatives (Pelling, 2007). More recently, PRA was used effectively in a 2025 island-wide volcanic preparedness study to align local knowledge with formal risk planning structures (Arevalo et al., 2025). Outcome Harvesting, on the other hand, has proven useful for capturing emergent outcomes in complex systems where linear monitoring frameworks fall short, characterized by iterative process, identifying early and otherwise hidden changes in the causal pathway and working backwards from observed outcomes (Wilson-Grau & Britt, 2012). The method has been successfully adapted for donor-funded development programmes as well as participatory community-led interventions, including CARE and USAID's 2024 adaptation of the method to support learning and reflection in resilience-building programmes (Smith, 2023).

As a complementary component to the data collection in 2.2.1 and 2.2.2, the PIM employs a participatory interview process aimed to identify, refine, and validate indicators that can be either quantitative or qualitative in nature. It is embedded within the broader SRM structure, ensuring that the insights it generates contribute directly to the indicator system. In practice, quantitative indicators derived from these interviews are preferred where feasible, providing measurable inputs to the SRM. However, in cases where quantitative data are unavailable or unsuitable, qualitative indicators are developed to ensure the continuity, inclusiveness, and contextual relevance of assessment. This approach maintains the SRM's robustness while enabling a comprehensive understanding of sustainability outcomes in diverse demonstrator settings.

At the core of the PIM is the reflective learning loop (RLL), a structured process that supports stakeholder engagement and critical reflection across six stages of the solution life cycle (Figure 2.3). The loop is structured around six interconnected phases: (1) Framing & Intention, (2) Design & Implementation, (3) Operation & Use, (4) Monitoring & Learning, (5) Looking Ahead, and (6) Indicator Reflection. Each phase corresponds to a specific stage of the solution life cycle and is supported by tailored question modules used during guided interviews. In the first phase, stakeholders reflect on the original goals, motivations, and expected outcomes of the solution. Subsequent phases capture real-world experiences, including implementation challenges, operational feedback, and changes prompted by community input or monitoring data. The fifth phase explores the anticipated future resilience of the solution—identifying critical risks and estimating how long benefits are likely to persist. Finally, the sixth phase provides a space to revisit and refine performance indicators, ensuring they remain relevant, measurable, and aligned with local and project-wide objectives. The cyclical nature of the loop promotes continuous learning, allowing lessons from later stages to inform future planning and decision-making. It also supports the co-development and validation of indicators in a way that is responsive to local realities, while maintaining coherence with the overall SRM.

Each phase prompts stakeholders to share practical experiences, identify enabling and constraining factors, and assess the sustainability and resilience capacity of the solution in context. The process emphasizes not only what was achieved, but how and why outcomes occurred—including unintended effects and adaptive responses. By cycling through each phase, the loop captures a comprehensive view of both performance and learning.

This method is particularly valuable for assessing transformational adaptation, where change is non-linear and uncertainty is high. It also supports indicator refinement by linking qualitative insights with quantitative frameworks, making the assessment more grounded, inclusive, and replicable in future applications or diverse operational environments.

Focus: Usefulness, relevance, and contribution of indicators

- Do the current indicators reflect what really matters in your context?
- Are there any indicators you would add, remove, or change?
- Which indicators best capture the solution's positive contributions (handprint)?
- Are these indicators aligned with local policy goals or community expectations?

(PRA Element: Risk-sensitive interpretation of indicator meaning)
(OH Element: Linking observed outcomes to indicator narratives)

Focus: Initial goals, expected outcomes, and pre-identified risks

- What problem or need was this solution designed to address?
- What were your original goals or success criteria?
- Who was involved in defining the solution and why?
- Were any risks or challenges foreseen at the outset?
- What outcomes were you hoping to see (in the short or long term)?

(PRA Element: Perceived vulnerabilities and risk assumptions)
(OH Element: Formulation of expected change pathways)

Focus: Resilience expectations and forward planning

- Which elements of the solution are most likely to continue working well?
- What external or internal risks could affect it in the future?
- How many years do you expect the solution to remain effective?
- How confident are you in its ability to adapt over time?

(PRA Element: Forward-looking risk mapping and response capacity)
(OH Element: Prospective outcomes and critical uncertainties)

Focus: Risk emergence, adaptation, and unintended consequences

- What went according to plan during implementation?
- What unexpected events or challenges emerged?
- How were those challenges addressed?
- Did you make any major changes to the - solution design or delivery?
- Were there any unintended positive or negative outcomes?

(PRA Element: Emergent risks and adaptive responses)
(OH Element: Outcomes that were not originally planned or predicted)

Focus: Reflection, local knowledge, and validation

- What kind of monitoring or evaluation was done?
- What did you learn from it?
- What were the biggest surprises—positive or negative?
- Did any feedback from stakeholders or users lead to changes in your approach?

(PRA Element: Participatory learning and validation)
(OH Element: Harvesting "who did what, when, and why?")

Focus: Current performance, user experience, and resilience signals

- Is the solution operating the way you intended?
- What signs, feedback, or data show that it is (or isn't) working?
- Are users, communities, or institutions engaging with the solution as expected?
- Are there any ongoing challenges or unexpected benefits?

(PRA Element: Operational exposure to stressors or risks)
(OH Element: Stakeholder behaviours or decisions influenced by the solution)

Figure 2.3 Reflective learning loop for participatory insights module

Box 2.2 Participatory insights module for Adaptation Fund in Guadeloupe, France

Participatory insights module (PIM) supports the development, refinement and validation of indicators, enabling grounded assessment of stakeholder engagement, governance, implementation performance, monitoring, and fund sustainability. It is used in one-on-one interviews with demonstrator involved in the development and implementation of the Adaptation Fund (AF) solution.

1. Framing & Intention

- What problem or funding gap was this adaptation fund designed to address?
- What were your original goals or success criteria for the fund (e.g. coverage, participation, financing)?
- Who was involved in designing the fund and what roles did they play?
- Were any risks or uncertainties anticipated in setting up or managing the fund?
- What kinds of impacts were you hoping the fund would create in the short and long term?

2. Design & Implementation

- What aspects of the fund setup and early implementation went as planned?
- What challenges emerged during the legal, institutional, or operational design process?
- How were public and private actors engaged in fund development and governance?
- Were there any changes in structure, process, or funding mechanisms due to evolving conditions?
- Did any unplanned or unexpected outcomes—positive or negative—arise during this phase?

3. Operation & Use

- Is the fund operating as originally intended in terms of process and access?
- What kind of support or guidance do applicants receive during the application phase?
- How do actual application and approval rates compare to initial expectations?
- Are public and private stakeholders engaging with the fund as planned?
- Are there recurring issues or unexpected benefits related to fund usage?

4. Monitoring & Learning

- What monitoring or evaluation has been conducted on fund processes or user satisfaction?
- What have you learned about stakeholder experience, participation, or satisfaction with the fund?
- What were the most surprising lessons—either challenges or successes—during implementation?
- Have any adjustments been made in response to stakeholder feedback or complaints?

5. Looking Ahead

- Which components of the fund (governance, financing, outreach) are most likely to remain functional over time?
- What risks—such as cost overruns, funding gaps, or coordination breakdowns—could affect its future success?
- How long do you expect the fund to remain operational without major redesign or new resources?
- How confident are you in the fund's ability to attract future investments or adapt to changing needs?

6. Indicator Reflection

- Do the current indicators used for monitoring the fund reflect what matters most in your context?
- Are there indicators you feel should be added, changed, or removed based on your experience?
- Which indicators best reflect the fund's positive contributions (e.g. participation, financing continuity, equity)?
- Are these indicators useful for learning, planning improvements, or communicating success?

Note: The PIM interview guide should be used in conjunction with the findings already captured in Sections 2.1.1 (Pre-Identified Information) and 2.2.2 (Monitoring and Solution-Specific Reports). Questions already covered through these previous data sources need not be repeated unless further clarification or contextual insight is required.

2.2.4 Life cycle assessment

LCA is a method for assessing the potential environmental impacts of products, processes, services, or organizations throughout their life cycle, from raw material extraction and manufacturing to use and disposal. Defined by ISO 14040 and ISO 14044, LCA focuses specifically on the environmental dimension of sustainability, helping identify hotspots and informing decisions to reduce environmental burdens. However, to fully assess sustainability, which includes environmental, social, and economic aspects, LCA should be complemented by other methodologies. Thus, implementing LCA as part of SRM enables the inclusion of detailed environmental impact assessment offered by LCA within the broader sustainability assessment provided by SRM. LCA consists of four main phases defined by ISO (Fig. 2.4): goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory, Life cycle impact assessment, and interpretation of the results. Importantly, LCA is not a linear but inherently iterative. Iteration may be required at any stage to refine the study based on data availability, methodological adjustments, or evolving objectives.

Figure 2.4 LCA phases according to ISO 14040:2006.

Goal and scope definition is the initial stage that establishes the purpose of the study, the intended application, and the intended audience. This ensures that the study addresses the right questions and clearly communicates its findings to the audience, making them actionable and influential. An important part of this phase is defining the function of the system, which refers to what the product, process, or service is meant to do in relation to the research question. Based on this, a functional unit is chosen as a consistent reference point for all calculations. The scope of the study is also defined at this stage. It includes setting system boundaries (what is included or excluded from the analysis), the level of detail, any assumptions made, and methodological choices. These elements are critical to ensure that the study is transparent, focused, and reliable.

Life cycle inventory (LCI) analysis. This stage involves systematic collection and quantification of data on all relevant inputs and outputs associated with a product system throughout its life cycle. Inputs may include raw materials, energy, and water, while outputs consist of emissions to air, water, and soil, as well as solid waste. The inventory should cover all stages defined in the scope of the study, such as raw material extraction, manufacturing, construction, use, maintenance and end-of-life treatment. Data can

be collected from primary sources such as direct measurements, industry databases, literature sources or expert estimates. It is essential to ensure that the data are representative, consistent, and aligned with the defined functional unit. Where primary data is not available, secondary data or proxies may be used. The quality and completeness of LCI is critical, as they directly influence the reliability of the subsequent impact assessment.

Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) stage involves evaluating the potential environmental impacts associated with the inputs and outputs identified in the LCI. The goal of LCIA is to translate material and energy flows into environmental impact categories using scientifically established methods. The process includes classification, where inventory data are assigned to relevant impact categories (e.g. climate change, eutrophication, acidification, resource depletion), and characterization, where these flows are quantified based on their relative contribution to each category. In TransformAr, midpoint indicators from the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.0 method were used for impact assessment in accordance with recommendations from the European Commission's Joint Research Center (JRC, 2019). The JRC has led the development to ensure scientific robustness, policy alignment, and harmonization across product categories. The midpoint impact categories provide a reliable basis for evaluating environmental performance across multiple impact areas. In TransformAr, midpoint impact categories from the LCA were used directly as indicators within the broader sustainability assessment. This approach makes it possible to capture both environmental impacts and benefits across the various environmental flows included in each impact category, providing a more complete and nuanced assessment of environmental performance.

Interpretation of the results. The interpretation phase involves analyzing the results from the impact assessment stage in relation to the defined goal and scope of the study. The main purpose of this stage is to identify significant issues, draw conclusions, and provide recommendations based on the findings. In practice, interpretation often leads to the refinement of earlier phases, such as narrowing system boundaries, improving data quality, or modifying allocation procedure.

In the context of the TransformAr project, LCA was selectively applied only to NBS. This methodological choice reflects the fact that NBS typically involve tangible material and energy flows, such as construction materials, filtration media, operational inputs, that can be tracked and quantified throughout their life cycle. These measurable flows are essential for conducting an LCA, which relies on inventory data to assess environmental impacts across various stages such as raw material extraction, construction, use, maintenance, and end-of-life. In contrast, other types of solutions implemented in the project (e.g., digital platforms, behavioral change initiatives, and governance schemes) lack discrete physical flows, making them unsuitable for quantitative LCA.

Box 2.3 LCA case study – Nature-Based Solution in Westcountry Region, UK

The NBS implemented at Chubbs Farm in the Westcountry Region, UK, focuses on floodplain reconnection and water quality improvement through a combination of interventions, including the installation of leaky dam cascades, wetland enhancement, and ditch blocking. These measures aim to slow the flow of agricultural runoff, enhance sediment retention, and reduce nutrient pollutions from upstream dairy farm activities.

1. Goal and scope definition

The goal of LCA is to assess the environmental impacts of this NBS across its full life cycle over a 20-year period. The assessment followed a cradle-to-grave approach, including the stages from material use and construction to operation and maintenance. The NBS performance was compared with a baseline scenario in which no intervention is implemented, and runoff remains untreated.

The functional unit is defined as the treatment of the runoff across the catchment area over 20 years. Based on precipitation data and land use characteristics, the annual runoff was estimated at approximately 140 000 m³. This figure was used as the basis for comparing environmental performance between scenarios.

System boundaries for the LCA of NBS

2. Life cycle inventory.

The life cycle inventory was compiled using a combination of sources provided by the WRT, on-site implementation data, and modeled assumptions. Emissions related to staff travel, chainsaw fuel consumption, and maintenance routines were calculated using Sphera database unit processes for transportation and fuel use. Water quality data were based on upstream and downstream sampling, while runoff volumes were estimated using local precipitation and land use data.

3. Impact assessment

The EF 3.0 method was used for impact assessment. The most relevant impact categories are climate change, eutrophication, ecotoxicity, and resource use.

Key Findings:

- 63% reduction in ecotoxicity (driven by ammonium reduction)
- 6% reduction in freshwater eutrophication
- Construction & maintenance impacts account for <4% of total emissions

Primary emissions from maintenance-related travel

4. Limitations

The LCA relied on several assumptions due to data limitations. The annual runoff volume was estimated based on precipitation and land cover data, and actual flow measurements would improve the precision of the analysis. Additionally, no sediment removal was modelled, although such activity may become necessary during the system's lifespan. Maintenance frequency was based on reasonable assumptions but may vary over time. The impacts from chainsaw production and a negligible amount of plastic waste were excluded.

2.3 Performance and indicator refinement

The performance and indicator refinement process in D5.7 builds upon a structured yet flexible approach that integrates implementation experience, stakeholder reflection, and comparative analysis across solution types. While the foundations for indicator development were established in D5.2 and the SRM in D5.9, this deliverable focuses on how these indicators were adapted and validated ex-post, based on real-world application and learning across the six TransformAr demonstrators.

The indicators used in this assessment emerged through iterative refinement informed by three types of evidence collected in Section 2.2. The insights gathered from these sources allowed demonstrators and TSPs to revisit the original intentions of each solution, assess actual performance, and reflect on which indicators most effectively captured both sustainability outcomes and resilience capacity. To navigate the diversity of solutions and operational contexts, the indicator refinement process aligned with the five AAS categories that were defined: Behavioural change and awareness-raising (BCAR), Governance Schemes (GS), Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), Technological and Digital Solutions (TDS), and Insurance, financial and economic schemes (IFE). These categories provided a useful framework for analyzing patterns in performance emphasis across different types of interventions. For example, indicators associated with BCAS and GS often focused on stakeholder engagement, institutional coordination, and awareness-raising, whereas those under TDS more frequently addressed aspects of system performance, data quality, and digital service delivery. By working within these established categories, the refinement process was able to identify both solution-specific indicator needs and cross-cutting performance themes that could inform a more harmonized and transferable assessment framework.

Indicators were harmonized within each solution category to allow for better comparability. This meant aligning terminology, adjusting granularity where necessary, and ensuring that scoring logic could be meaningfully applied across demonstrators using similar types of interventions. Following this intra-category harmonization, a second round of cross-category analysis was conducted to identify broader performance categories that could be used across solution types. This effort resulted in the development

of a refined set of performance categories, validated in D5.9, and used consistently throughout this deliverable. These categories were designed to strike a balance between context-specific relevance and methodological generalizability, enabling more consistent evaluation of diverse solutions while still allowing for solution-specific nuances.

A heatmap shows the frequency of each performance category applied across the five AAS categories in Figure 2.4. It provides a snapshot of indicator distribution and methodological alignment across solution types.

Figure 2.4 Performance category vs. actionable adaptive solutions (AAS) by category Behavioural change and awareness-raising (BCAR), Governance Schemes (GS), Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), Technological and Digital Solutions (TDS), and Insurance, financial and economic schemes (IFE).

Categories such as Risk and Resilience, Financial Viability, Management and Coordination, and Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation, are highly represented across all solution types—suggesting that these domains are broadly relevant and methodologically mature for assessing adaptation outcomes. Conversely, some performance categories show a strong solution-specific concentration. For instance, Water Quality, Biodiversity and Habitat, Flood Vulnerability and Livability and Comfort are primarily used in NBS, reflecting their ecological and site-specific character. Meanwhile, System Performance and Data Quality are most heavily represented in TSD, where operational efficiency and data reliability are central to impact.

To ensure both the usability and credibility of the assessment, the refinement of performance categories and indicators in D5.7 was guided by a consistent set of quality considerations. These criteria served as

principles kept in mind throughout the iterative development, validation, and co-reflection with demonstrators and TSPs. These criteria helped shape judgments on which indicators to retain, revise, or generalize, ensuring coherence across the broader SRM. They included:

- Relevance to sustainability objectives and the local risk and policy context
- Measurability and clarity in terms of data availability and monitoring practicality
- Adaptability across different types of solutions, regions, and institutional settings
- Alignment with SDGs and TransformAr’s strategic aims
- Interpretability for local stakeholders, ensuring that indicators are actionable and meaningful

These guiding criteria were not used to filter out indicators through a formal scoring mechanism. Instead, they shaped the iterative dialogues and analytical synthesis across solution categories, helping ensure that each performance category and its associated indicators could serve both local insight and project-wide comparability.

The outcome is a set of refined performance categories and solution-specific indicators that are sensitive to local implementation realities while still allowing for generalization and replication. These indicators reflect both the sustainability outcomes achieved and the adaptive capacity built through each solution’s journey.

By embedding these considerations in a participatory, evidence-informed process, D5.7 reinforces that indicators are not static or one-size-fits-all. They are living tools—evolving with practice, responsive to new risks and opportunities, and co-owned by the actors who use them to track and improve sustainability outcomes. This refined set of performance categories and indicators forms the foundation for the resilience assessment in Section 3 and the demonstrator-level evaluation in Section 4, supporting a credible and transferable approach to evaluating transformational adaptation across diverse operational environments.

3 Resilience Assessment

Resilience is increasingly recognized as a critical attribute of climate adaptation solutions. In D5.7, resilience assessment refers to the capacity of solutions to maintain functionality and deliver intended benefits under evolving climate and socio-institutional conditions. The assessment builds on the SRM indicators developed in D5.2 and D5.9, applying them through a structured, participatory process to evaluate three dimensions—Relevance, Confidence, and Timespan. This enables site-specific reflection and fosters transparent, evidence-informed evaluation and supports strategic learning, prioritization, and future planning across the TransformAr demonstrators.

3.1 Resilience capacity

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) defines resilience as: “the capacity of social, economic, and environmental systems to cope with a hazardous event or trend or disturbance, responding or reorganizing in ways that maintain their essential function, identity, and structure, while also maintaining the capacity for adaptation, learning, and transformation” (IPCC, 2014)

In the context of climate adaptation and sustainability transitions, resilience capacity is a critical concept. It denotes the specific capabilities of a solution or system to manage climate-related risks over time. The resilience capacity of a solution can be broken down in three interlinked components (Béné et al., 2012; Tanner et al., 2017), show in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Resilience as the result of absorptive, adaptive and transformative capacities

Absorptive coping capacity reflects the ability of a solution to maintain stability and persist through stressors without significant changes to its core structure or function. As resilience demands increase, systems may require adaptive capacity—defined by their flexibility and capacity for incremental adjustments. This enables the system to evolve without losing its identity. At the highest end of the spectrum is transformative capacity, which involves systemic and structural changes that enable a solution to respond effectively to fundamentally altered conditions. These capacities are associated with increasing levels of change, investment, and strategic planning, forming a comprehensive framework for resilience assessment (Béné et al., 2012). Each of these capacities contributes to overall resilience, depending on the intensity and nature of the disturbance. Climate resilience capacity thus requires a systemic assessment, considering socio-technical, environmental, institutional, and economic dimensions.

In TransformAr, resilience capacity is defined as the forward-looking potential of a solution to sustain its intended benefits under future uncertainty, based on its demonstrated relevance to key resilience functions, the confidence in its sustained performance, and the anticipated duration of these benefits. This practical definition builds directly on the operational structure presented in the following 3.2 to 3.4: it reflects not only theoretical foundations from IPCC and resilience literature but also embeds the TransformAr-specific methodology grounded in indicator-based scoring and participatory validation. It supports integrated, lifecycle-informed assessments that help anticipate system responses to evolving climate risks—thus aligning solution design, monitoring, and scaling with long-term transformational adaptation objectives.

3.2 Indicators and dimensions

To ensure consistency and comparability across deliverables, the resilience assessment in D5.7 builds on the same indicator base developed through the SRM in D5.2 and D5.9. This approach avoids duplication and leverages indicators that have already been validated and refined through implementation experience. The use of SRM indicators for resilience assessment is based on the principle of methodological consistency and data efficiency across TransformAr's evaluation framework. These indicators were developed to reflect key sustainability criteria, which inherently overlap with resilience considerations, particularly in the context of complex socio-technical systems operating under climate stress. By reapplying SRM indicators through the lens of resilience, the methodology ensures coherence with life cycle and systems thinking, enables comparative analysis across both sustainability and resilience dimensions, and supports integrated decision-making for transformative adaptation.

The rationale for using SRM indicators includes:

- **Continuity:** Aligning sustainability and resilience assessment in a single, integrated framework ensures methodological consistency. For example, the indicator Phosphate Credit Implementation Readiness, used in the GB (Green Bonds) solution, assesses readiness of fiscal mechanisms and their alignment with climate goals. Its inclusion in resilience assessment reflects the robustness of systemic financial structures under future stress conditions.
- **Efficiency:** Reusing indicators that stakeholders are already familiar with reduces the learning curve and streamlines data collection. For instance, the indicator Event Attendance, used in the AWAR (Awareness-Raising Modules) solution, captures levels of stakeholder involvement. Reuse in resilience scoring allows assessment of social cohesion and community responsiveness during disruptions.
- **Scalability:** Shared indicators enable comparability across diverse sites and solutions. For example, the indicator Survey, used in the CAF (Citizen App Finland) solution, is a flexible tool for feedback collection. It can be replicated across contexts to assess institutional learning and participatory adaptation.
- **Ownership:** Involving demonstrators in the co-development of SRM indicators fosters stronger engagement and credibility. For instance, the indicator Workshop, used in the CIH (Climate Innovation Hub) solution, reflects participatory design and capacity building. This directly contributes to resilience through shared knowledge and institutional memory across local stakeholders.

However, not all indicators are equally suited to resilience assessment. For example, a solution like CEI (citizen survey tool) in Lappeenranta, which supports awareness and participation, was not evaluated for resilience capacity because it does not represent a stable or time-dependent function that persists under changing conditions. In contrast, solutions with material, institutional, or service components (e.g., natural based solution, digital monitoring, financial schemes) lend themselves more naturally to resilience scoring.

There are three dimensions—Relevance, Confidence, and Timespan—to define the resilience capacity of a solution, Figure 3.2. Each dimension plays a distinct role: Relevance identifies whether a function is essential, Confidence measures certainty in its continuation under change, and Timespan evaluates the longevity of its benefit. Their convergence represents a holistic, forward-looking understanding of resilience within the TransformAR assessment framework.

- **Relevance:** Does this indicator reflect a key function or property that contributes to the solution’s ability to be resilient? For instance, access to local resources or institutional support mechanisms may indicate the potential to persist or adapt.
- **Confidence:** How certain are demonstrators and TSPs that this function or benefit will continue under uncertain or changing conditions? This includes expert judgment and empirical evidence.
- **Timespan:** For how long (in years) is the benefit or performance expected to remain stable or grow? This includes the expected lifespan of physical solution components (e.g., technology systems) as well as the sustained performance of supporting processes, partnerships, and institutional arrangements that underpin the solution’s delivery over time.

Figure 3.2 Dimensions of resilience assessment of a solution

These dimensions allow for forward-looking judgments that go beyond current performance levels. Consistent with the structured PIM approach described in Section 2, they were introduced during interviews to guide reflective, evidence-informed scoring for each indicator. Where evidence was limited (e.g., for pilot solutions or one-time campaigns), indicators were either excluded or annotated with limitations. The assessment prioritizes functions that are expected to persist, interact with other system components, or require ongoing adaptation.

Applying this indicator-based assessment framework across the demonstrators provided valuable operational insights. The structure enabled the inclusion of diverse solutions—ranging from technical systems to digital platforms and social mechanisms—within a consistent methodology. Demonstrators noted that combining sustainability and resilience dimensions enabled a richer understanding of each solution’s performance over time and under stress.

The self-assessment method, supported by TSPs, also encouraged ownership and critical analysis. For example, the dimension of “Confidence” helped expose underlying assumptions about institutional stability, partner continuity, or long-term commitment. “Timespan” stimulated practical conversations on how long a solution’s benefits would remain effective, especially for early-phase or pilot projects.

Furthermore, the process underscored the importance of aligning local experience with broader project knowledge. Demonstrators used institutional memory, stakeholder input, and scenario thinking to justify scores. When uncertainties arose, TSPs provided context by referencing comparable experiences across the consortium. This iterative scoring method helped balance subjective judgments with shared learning.

Some demonstrators expressed interest in reapplying this evaluation in future adaptation planning, both to benchmark resilience improvements over time and to communicate solution maturity to policymakers or funders. Importantly, combining sustainability and resilience views helped identify trade-offs: some highly sustainable solutions were found to have limited long-term resilience, while others showed robustness despite lower sustainability scores. This illustrates the necessity of integrating both assessments in decision-making processes to ensure durable, climate-ready innovations.

3.3 Evaluation Process

The resilience assessment was implemented as a self-evaluation process carried out by each Demonstrator in collaboration with their TSP. Depending on availability and context, the process was supported in one or more of the following ways:

- A scoring template with examples for each of the three dimensions.
- Facilitated validation meetings to clarify doubts and align interpretations across teams.
- Detailed recording instructions for each scoring entry, ensuring that justifications were traceable.

These support mechanisms were applied on a case-by-case basis, according to the needs and resources of each site. Demonstrators and TSPs selected relevant indicators and assigned scores using a combination of monitoring data, stakeholder input, observed performance, and institutional knowledge. The scoring process was often iterative, with teams refining entries as new evidence or perspectives became available.

This co-evaluation approach ensured that assessments were both context-sensitive and methodologically consistent, allowing local insight to inform project-wide resilience analysis. Where uncertainties emerged, TSPs contributed additional context and cross-demonstrator learning. This encouraged shared understanding, critical reflection, and greater ownership of results, strengthening the foundation for the resilience capacity evaluation presented in the following section.

To provide an accessible overview of the evaluation, the four-step process applied in the resilience capacity evaluation is illustrated in the radial diagram in Figure 3.3. Each segment represents a distinct yet interconnected phase of the assessment cycle. This circular format reinforces the iterative and systemic nature of the process—demonstrating how indicator selection, scoring, calculation, and validation collectively contributes to building robust and context-specific resilience profiles. The steps include:

1. Indicator relevance mapping – identifying relevant functions,
2. Scoring across dimensions – assessing Relevance, Confidence, and Timespan,
3. Profiling and integration – synthesizing scores for resilience insight,
4. Validation and iteration – ensuring consistency and credibility.

This structured flow enables the integration of diverse evidence sources and expert judgment, while supporting transparency and comparability across the TransformAr demonstrators.

Figure 3.3 Four steps of resilience capacity evaluation

Step 1: Indicator relevance mapping – identifying relevant functions

The first step in assessing resilience capacity involves identifying which indicators meaningfully represent the functions essential to a solution’s ability to respond under changing conditions. This process builds on the refined indicators already developed and validated through the SRM in D5.2 and D5.9. The goal is to filter from these indicators those that are most critical to resilience, those that signal performance continuity, response flexibility, or structural robustness.

This mapping is solution-specific and context-aware. Demonstrators together with their TSPs, reviewed their indicator sets to determine which ones reflected key resilience-related dimensions such as institutional commitment, stakeholder responsiveness, system flexibility, or funding continuity. Indicators related only to short-term outputs or context-specific actions were typically excluded unless they had broader implications for system stability.

By focusing on functions, rather than thematic categories alone, this step ensures that the resilience assessment remains functionally grounded and forward-looking. The selected indicators serve as the basis for subsequent scoring across dimensions, and ultimately for profiling the overall resilience capacity of each solution. This ensures the analysis remains both relevant to local challenges and transferable across different adaptive contexts.

Step 2: Scoring across dimensions – assessing Relevance, Confidence, and Timespan

For each retained indicator, the evaluation proceeded with systematic scoring across the three dimensions—Relevance, Confidence, and Timespan. This step was central to the assessment framework, providing a structured basis for evaluating the resilience capacity of each solution. Scores were assigned on a scale from 1 (low) to 5 (high), based on shared judgments formed through collaborative discussion between each Demonstrator and their TSP.

- **Relevance** assessed the degree to which the indicator reflected an essential function or property contributing to resilience. Scoring was guided by prompts related to the indicator’s connection to core benefits, exposure to climate risks, and potential for maintaining system performance under future uncertainty.
- **Confidence** captured the level of certainty that the solution’s benefits will persist. Demonstrator and TSP considered past experience, maturity of implementation, stakeholder reliability, and

presence of redundant or supporting systems. Confidence scoring was particularly useful for identifying areas where assumptions may outweigh evidence, such as in newly implemented solutions.

- **Timespan** evaluated how long the benefits of the solution or function were expected to last. This included technical durability, likelihood of sustained user behaviour, policy continuity, or ecosystem performance over time. Though not weighted into the final score, Timespan helped contextualize short- vs long-term contributions to resilience.

An important feature of this step is its emphasis on co-reflection rather than solely technical scoring. The qualitative nature of these dimensions required that Demonstrators and TSPs combine empirical evidence with local insight, institutional knowledge, and practical judgment. Scoring was encouraged to be iterative, particularly in cases where data limitations or uncertainties emerged. Teams were prompted to revisit and refine scores based on stakeholder feedback, updated monitoring results, or comparison with peer demonstrators facing similar conditions. This iterative approach ensured that the resulting evaluations reflected not only observed performance but also evolving understanding of solution functionality and resilience potential. The structured process supported consistency across demonstrators while allowing for meaningful local adaptation in how scores were interpreted and justified.

Step 3: Profiling and integration – synthesizing scores for resilience insight,

The resilience capacity score for each solution was calculated through a structured methodology using the scored indicators. Each indicator’s Relevance score (rated from 1 - Very low relevance to 5 - Critically relevant) was first used to define a weight reflecting its functional significance within the solution. These weights were then used to calculate a weighted average of the Confidence scores (also rated from 1 - Very low Confidence to 5 - Critically Confident), which capture the perceived certainty that each function will persist under changing conditions.

The formula used for calculating the resilience capacity score for a was as follows:

$$Resilience\ Capacity = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(Confidence_i \times \frac{Relevance_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n Relevance_i} \right)$$

Where,

Resilience Capacity – the overall resilience capacity score of a solution,

n – total number of indicators selected as relevant to resilience,

Relevance_i – the Relevance score assigned to indicator *i*, reflecting importance to resilience,

Confidence_i – the Confidence score assigned to indicators *i*, reflecting certainty that the function or benefit will persist.

The overall resilience capacity score for the solution was then calculated as the sum of all Weighted Confidence scores, effectively giving greater influence on highly relevant indicators. The maximum possible score is 5, reflecting an ideal composite across all dimensions. Interpretation of the resulting profiles is further elaborated in Section 3.4.

Timespan was not used in this numerical calculation but was recorded alongside each indicator to support interpretative insight into long-term benefit. This allowed teams to contextualize whether a highly resilient function was expected to endure for years or was short-lived in nature.

This approach avoids assigning solutions to rigid, predefined resilience categories. Instead, it produces a continuous, indicator-based score that reflects observed and expected performance across contextually

relevant and validated indicators. The method is designed to accommodate variation in solution type, implementation setting, and data availability, making it flexible and adaptable to real-world constraints.

Final scores were calculated using a shared spreadsheet template with integrated formulas to reduce manual error and promote consistency across demonstrators. Each scoring entry was jointly reviewed by Demonstrators and their TSPs to ensure that high or low values were well justified, assumptions were explicitly noted, and results aligned with practical experience and solution-specific knowledge.

By combining structured templates with iterative co-evaluation, this method balances clarity, customization, and analytical rigor. It offers a transparent, scalable, and forward-looking approach to resilience capacity assessment that fits within the broader TransformAr evaluation framework. Importantly, it facilitates comparative insight across diverse solutions without relying on subjective categorization into static resilience types—preserving both methodological coherence and the flexibility needed for diverse adaptation contexts.

Step 4: Validation and Iteration – Ensuring Consistency and Credibility

The final step in the resilience assessment process focused on validating the scoring outputs and refining them through collaborative reflection. This step was essential to ensure that results were not only internally coherent and methodologically consistent across demonstrators, but also credible and reflective of the lived realities of implementation.

Validation was conducted in a participatory manner, with Demonstrators and their TSPs jointly reviewing the full set of scores and accompanying justifications. The aim was to identify outliers, clarify ambiguous entries, and confirm that scoring decisions were well-grounded in evidence, experience, or a combination of both. In some cases, discussions during this stage could lead to updates of initial entries—either to align with new data, reinterpreted stakeholder insights, or cross-checks with other demonstrators operating under similar conditions.

Importantly, this step did not impose uniformity but supported transparency and traceability. Where high or low scores were maintained, demonstrators were encouraged to clearly explain their reasoning. This enriched the learning value of the assessment and ensured that future users, whether within or beyond the TransformAr project, could interpret results with confidence.

The iterative nature of this step also allowed for the integration of new information over time. As more monitoring data became available or institutional understanding evolved, teams had the opportunity to revisit and refine their evaluations. This iterative design is particularly important in the context of climate adaptation, where resilience capacity is not a fixed trait but one that must evolve in response to dynamic environmental and socio-political conditions.

Ultimately, the validation and iteration process enhanced both the credibility and usability of the resilience assessment. It reinforced the importance of stakeholder ownership, methodological transparency, and the ability to adapt the evaluation framework to a range of operational realities. These qualities are vital for supporting the replication and scaling of TransformAr solutions across diverse contexts.

Box 3.1 Resilience capacity evaluation from Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM) in Galicia, Spain MAM

The MRM initiative represents a pioneering step towards the digitalization of mussel aquaculture, integrating real-time environmental and production monitoring to enhance farm management and sustainability. A total of 48 indicators and sub-indicators were originally developed, spanning 7 performance categories: Stakeholder Engagement and Participation, System Performance, Data Quality, Monitoring, Evaluation and Adaptation, Management and Coordination, Financial Viability, and Risk and Resilience (details in D5.2)

In Step 1: Indicator Relevance Mapping, 14 indicators and sub-indicators were identified as directly contributing to resilience and mapped across 6 of the performance categories. **In Step 2: Scoring Across Dimensions**, each selected indicator was assessed for Relevance and Confidence, using a structured 1–5 scale. The Demonstrator also estimated a **Timespan** of two years for the expected duration of benefit from these indicators. **In Step 3: Profiling and Integration**, the final resilience capacity score was calculated as 4.10 out of 5, based on the sum of Weighted Confidence scores. **Step 4: Validation and Iteration** involved facilitated discussions and meeting review with the Demonstrator. The preliminary results were then re-examined through an iterative process, allowing the Demonstrator to collect additional information, clarify assumptions, and reflect on indicator scoring. In close collaboration with the TSP, the scores were refined and finalized, then submitted via SharePoint for consolidation and interpretation, as presented in Section 4.3 of this report.

Performance categories	Indicator	Sub-indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Weighting	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence
Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Shellfish Sector Publications/Outputs		4	9 %	4	0,37
	Risks and Adaptation Awareness Increase		5	12 %	4	0,47
	Population that enhance resilience		5	12 %	4	0,47
	Actors involved in the adaptive process		5	12 %	5	0,58
Data Quality	Continuous monitoring		5	12 %	5	0,58
	Data Accuracy	Data Accuracy Rate	4	9 %	3	0,28
		Data Accuracy Satisfaction	5	12 %	4	0,47
	Environmental Data Access		4	9 %	3,5	0,33
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Stakeholder Use of Data		4	9 %	4	0,37
	Data Satisfaction		4	9 %	4	0,37
Management and Coordination	Traditional Knowledge Integration		5	12 %	4	0,47
	Stakeholder Coordination		5	12 %	5	0,58
Financial Viability	Maintenance	Maintenance cost	3	7 %	5	0,35
Risk and Resilience	Environmental Challenges		4	9 %	2,5	0,23

3.4 Interpretation and uncertainties

The resilience capacity scores derived through the indicator-based evaluation process represent a structured approximation of each solution's potential to perform under changing conditions. However, like any self-assessment or evidence-informed framework, the outputs must be interpreted with care. This section outlines how the results should be understood, what they reveal about system performance, and what uncertainties remain.

Interpreting the resilience capacity score

The final resilience capacity score for each solution is calculated from the sum of all weighted Confidence scores, where each indicator's score for Confidence is multiplied by its Relevance rating. This approach ensures that indicators deemed highly relevant have a stronger influence on the total outcome. The maximum possible composite score is 5, indicating a solution with consistently high relevance, strong evidence of reliable performance, and a high level of stakeholder certainty regarding its continued functionality.

However, these scores are not meant to rank solutions competitively. Instead, they offer a profile of resilience attributes across a solution's key functions, highlighting both strengths and potential vulnerabilities. For example, a solution may receive a high overall score but still reveal a short expected Timespan for certain critical functions, pointing to areas where durability or long-term institutional support may be lacking. Conversely, a moderate total score combined with high Confidence ratings and long Timespans may suggest robustness in key dimensions even if other indicators are still evolving.

Thus, interpretation must move beyond the numeric output to consider:

- Which functions are driving the overall score;
- Where the most uncertainty or short-term expectations exist;
- How Relevance-weighted scoring elevates critical but potentially fragile aspects of the solution.

This qualitative dimension of interpretation ensures that the resilience score serves not only as an evaluation tool but also as a prompt for strategic learning and adaptive planning.

Disaggregated interpretation by dimension

Breaking down scores by each of the three resilience dimensions—Relevance, Confidence, and Timespan—yields further insights. For instance:

- High Relevance and low Confidence may indicate that a function is central to resilience but lacks sufficient institutional support, technical reliability, or operational data.
- High Confidence but short Timespan suggests solutions that work well now but may lack sustainable structures, long-term financing, or regulatory backing.
- Medium Relevance with high Confidence and long Timespan could signal solid functions that are not necessarily resilience-critical but offer stable support for overall performance.

This dimensional breakdown is particularly valuable in identifying where targeted interventions could enhance resilience, e.g., by improving the robustness of a highly relevant but currently uncertain function.

Role of Timespan in contextualizing resilience

While the Timespan dimension was not included in the aggregated score calculation, it serves an important interpretive role. Solutions with short Timespan estimates, typically less than two years, may face greater exposure to discontinuities in funding, political support, or user behaviour. Identifying such

risks early can guide demonstrators in developing continuity strategies, whether through policy alignment, stakeholder re-engagement, or technical upgrades.

In contrast, long Timespan ratings suggest confidence in durability and systemic embedding, which is especially important for infrastructure-based or institutional solutions. However, even long-duration expectations must be accompanied by strong Confidence ratings to avoid overestimating resilience based on aspirations rather than grounded evidence.

Sources and types of uncertainty

Despite the structured approach, uncertainty remains inherent in resilience assessment, particularly in forward-looking estimates that involve judgment and projection. Three broad categories of uncertainty are relevant:

- Data uncertainty

Variability in data quality, availability, or comparability across Demonstrators can affect scoring confidence. Some indicators were supported by robust monitoring data, while others relied on stakeholder perception or qualitative assessment.

- Perceptual and cognitive uncertainty

As a co-evaluation process, scoring is shaped by the knowledge, assumptions, and interpretations of participants. Differences in institutional maturity, sectoral familiarity, or risk tolerance can lead to variation in how scores are assigned—even for similar types of solutions.

- Contextual uncertainty

The dynamic nature of climate, policy, and economic systems means that future performance cannot be predicted with certainty. A solution considered resilient today may become vulnerable under different institutional or environmental conditions.

Managing and communicating uncertainty

To manage these uncertainties, the process emphasizes transparency of assumptions. Each scoring entry shall be accompanied by a rationale describing the basis for the judgment—whether data-driven, experience-based, or informed by consultation. This allows for interpretation that is not only evidence-informed but also traceable.

Furthermore, the use of participatory validation (see Section 3.3) helped triangulate perspectives, reduce blind spots, and surface areas of divergence. In this way, uncertainty is not seen as a limitation, but as an opportunity to generate deeper understanding of resilience dynamics, both within and across Demonstrators.

When used cautiously and with full appreciation of its structure, the resilience capacity profile becomes a strategic tool. It can help demonstrators in 1) Prioritize areas for improvement, 2) Identify critical functions needing long-term support, and 3) Communicate evidence of adaptive capacity to funders, policymakers, or communities. At the same time, the methodology remains open to refinement. As more data become available or new indicators emerge, scores can be revisited and profiles adjusted—ensuring that resilience assessment evolves with the solutions it is designed to support.

4 Resilience Evaluation by Demonstrator

This section presents a detailed assessment of how climate adaptation solutions contribute to resilience across the six TransformAr demonstrators. For each demonstrator, the analysis introduces the local context and climate challenges, followed by an evaluation of solution resilience performance. Subsequent synthesis sections analyze cross-demonstrator patterns by solution category and general trends and insights. The purpose is to identify what works, where evidence is strong or limited, and how performance measurement can be refined. These insights aim to guide context-sensitive interventions and improve the robustness and comparability of future resilience assessments. The details of scoring for each solution by demonstrator are presented in Annex.

4.1 Lappeenranta, Finland

The city of Lappeenranta, located in southeastern Finland on the shores of Lake Saimaa, is responding proactively to emerging climate risks, particularly those related to urban water management, environmental degradation, and stakeholder engagement. The city is experiencing increasing urban flood risks, stormwater pollution, and seasonal runoff variability due to climate change. Heavier and more frequent rainfall events, combined with aging drainage infrastructure, are placing strain on urban stormwater systems. These pressures not only threaten infrastructure but also pose a risk to Lake Saimaa's water quality, which is already challenged by nutrient loads, metals, and pollutants carried by surface runoff. Additionally, there is a recognized need to strengthen citizen awareness and participation in climate adaptation to improve long-term societal resilience.

The city's climate adaptation strategy is centered around two closely interconnected KCS: Urban Planning and Water Management, both of which are under increasing pressure due to climate change and urbanization.

1. **Urban Planning:** Urban planning in Lappeenranta is directly challenged by climate-driven extreme events, especially those involving surface water and snowmelt. Floodwaters and melting snow transport contaminants such as microplastics, oils, nutrients, and organic matter, which degrade water quality in both urban areas and Lake Saimaa. As winters become warmer and wetter due to climate change, more precipitation arrives as rain, intensifying runoff impacts. Located on the shores of this unique lake system, Lappeenranta depends on Lake Saimaa for recreation, tourism, and industrial activities, making water quality protection a priority that must be addressed through integrated urban planning.
2. **Water Management:** Effective water management is central to addressing the city's climate resilience challenges. Lake Saimaa serves as a drinking water source, yet its ecological condition is under threat from nutrient loading and eutrophication. The city has made strategic commitments to protecting biodiversity and aquatic ecosystems. However, the current stormwater infrastructure requires structural upgrades, network rehabilitation, and innovative approaches to stormwater treatment and control. These changes are critical to ensuring long-term environmental quality, ecosystem health, and public safety.

To address these challenges, Lappeenranta has deployed four complementary AAS. Three of these have been evaluated for the resilience capacity:

- **URB (Nature-based urban stormwater solution):** A biofiltration area in the city center that slows, filters, and absorbs runoff using natural processes. It mitigates flooding, improves water quality, and enhances biodiversity.

- SWMM (Stormwater monitoring): A digital monitoring system combining real-time sensors to track flow volumes, pollutant levels, and system stress, enabling data-driven stormwater management.
- CAF (Citizen App Finland): A mobile app that displays environmental data and enables citizens to provide feedback, report anomalies, and increase situational awareness. It is integrated into the municipal platform StreetAI.
- CEI (Choice Experiment Initiative) (not assessed for resilience as does not represent a stable or time-dependent function that persists or evolves under changing conditions): A survey-based tool exploring citizen preferences and willingness to implement stormwater adaptation measures on private properties. It supports planning but does not directly influence operational resilience.

The three solutions form a systemic resilience strategy addressing interconnected urban challenges. URB delivers the core environmental benefits through stormwater mitigation and water quality improvement. SWMM provides the monitoring and data infrastructure that enables real-time system oversight and supports adaptive management. CAF reinforces institutional and social resilience by enhancing civic engagement, participatory feedback, and transparent communication. These solutions are not designed to operate in isolation; rather, they function as a complementary portfolio. SWMM strengthens the effectiveness of URB through performance validation, while CAF amplifies public ownership and institutional responsiveness. This integrated approach fosters long-term adaptive capacity, with community involvement and cross-sectoral alignment supporting sustained resilience across environmental, technical, and governance domains.

The resilience capacity of the three solutions is assessed with bubble size representing the number of relevant indicators under the performance category. URB achieved the highest resilience capacity score (4.75), followed by CAF (4.74) and SWMM (3.48). The estimated Timespans are ten years for URB, five years for CAF, and three years for SWMM, reflecting their varying levels of institutional integration, technical maturity, and expected durability. The following analysis explores each solution's profile in detail, highlighting the key indicators driving resilience, data uncertainties, and complementary system roles.

Nature-based Urban Stormwater Solution (URB)

Resilience capacity score: 4,75 with 10 years Timespan

Summary

URB's profile is driven by indicators of high Relevance that also benefit from strong data/evidence support, leading to high Confidence. This alignment suggests that the solution not only targets key resilience functions but also delivers them in a credible, verifiable manner. However, the proxy nature of some environmental data introduces data-related uncertainty, and the operational complexity may require ongoing monitoring and adaptive maintenance. Overall, the URB solution demonstrates durable and impactful contributions to resilience, firmly embedded in Lappeenranta's institutional and ecological systems.

🔍 The URB solution emerged with the highest resilience capacity score (4.75). This outcome stems from its strong alignment with Lappeenranta’s core urban climate risks—particularly stormwater management, pollution control, and flood vulnerability. The solution’s design tackles both runoff reduction and water quality improvement. Highly relevant performance categories include "Flood Vulnerability," with indicators such as reduction in peak flow, and "Water Quality," assessed through nutrient and metal load reductions. These indicators directly contribute to SDGs 6, 11, and 13 and reflect measurable impacts, despite acknowledged uncertainties due to proxy water sampling and seasonal construction disturbances. Confidence in URB’s data remains strong, owing to the use of real-time sensors and laboratory analyses, and institutional capacity is bolstered by cross-departmental coordination and integration into long-term planning. Notably, URB also spans the environmental, social, and economic domains, with co-benefits in biodiversity, urban aesthetics, and avoided drainage system costs. With 12 out of 24 indicators assessed as relevant, and a projected operational Timespan of 10 years, URB offers a robust foundation for sustained resilience.

Stormwater Monitoring (SWMM)

Summary

SWMM’s value emerges from its capacity to amplify other solutions by providing accurate, timely data. This data enables both URB’s environmental management and CAF’s citizen feedback functions. Its resilience profile illustrates how operational enablers, while not directly transformative, are pivotal to systemic resilience. However, the short Timespan and medium Confidence highlight the need for institutional commitment to scaling, redundancy, and user training.

🔍 SWMM presents a resilience capacity score of 3.48, reflecting a technically specialized contribution. Rather than delivering direct impact, its strength lies in its role as an enabling solution that supports broader system functionality. Its relevance is moderated by the nature of its indicators, which are focused on system uptime, sensor performance, and data handling — factors essential for monitoring, but less directly tied to human or ecological outcomes. The monitoring system has shown high availability and adaptability, but initial issues such as data loss due to manhole leakage, dependence on a single sensor, and a two-hour delay in data transmission reduce its responsiveness

in real-time scenarios. Furthermore, although the platform is integrated with municipal data systems and technically scalable, its short-projected timespan (3 years) and limited accessibility to non-technical users constrain its capacity to contribute to long-term urban resilience. In general, SWMM's strength lies in its enabling functions supporting the other solutions—rather than in direct resilience delivery.

Citizen App Finland (CAF)

Summary

CAF's profile shows how social technologies can serve as resilience multipliers by empowering communities, enabling transparency, and bridging information gaps. Its indicators are highly relevant to civic participation and accountability, and the strong Confidence score suggests sustained operational effectiveness. Yet, the solution's impact remains sensitive to institutional coordination, digital literacy, and continuous feedback loops. These factors require close attention to ensure continued legitimacy and user engagement.

CAF achieved a resilience capacity score of 4.74, which operates in the domain of social and institutional resilience. It enhances participatory governance and real-time stakeholder communication. Indicators are primarily relevant to Usability, Utilization and user Engagement of the app. These indicators correspond closely with SDGs 11, 16, and 17, highlighting CAF's alignment with inclusive, transparent, and community-responsive adaptation. The app has already demonstrated its capacity to integrate public input, e.g., via feedback loops—and enables citizens to participate in environmental monitoring efforts. While usage remains somewhat localized, the intention to broaden access and engagement will strengthen future potential. CAF's confidence score (4.71) is supported by institutional integration (via StreetAI), technical development maturity, and the combination of real-time data and community involvement. A mid-term horizon of 5 years reflects a reasonable lifecycle for a digital platform, provided that institutional interest, funding, and technical support remain in place. While short relative to physical infrastructure, this duration is appropriate for a solution operating in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

In synthesis, the assessment reveals a well-structured resilience landscape in Lappeenranta. URB delivers ecosystem-based, infrastructure-level resilience rooted in physical risk mitigation. CAF strengthens social and governance dimensions, ensuring that adaptation remains inclusive and informed. SWMM, while

more limited in immediate resilience impact, underpins the effectiveness of both URB and CAF by providing the data backbone for monitoring and evaluation. The integration of these solutions—will continue through the BALTFLOOD project (Baltic Flood Resilience and Digital Solutions, funded by Interreg, 3/2025–2/2028)—demonstrates a systemic approach to climate resilience, with each solution reinforcing the others' performance and adaptability. This balanced portfolio, with differentiated but interlinked strengths, places Lappeenranta in a strong position to navigate both current challenges and future climate uncertainties

4.2 Westcountry Region, UK

The Westcountry region in South West England covers approximately 23,800 km², bordered by the Atlantic Ocean to the north and west and the English Channel to the south and east. Characterized by its rural catchments and coastal exposure, the region faces mounting climate risks driven by more frequent and extreme weather events. Projections by the UK Met Office highlight a future of hotter, drier summers and warmer, wetter winters, with increased risks of river and surface water flooding, droughts, pollution, landslides, and heatwaves. These impacts threaten not only natural ecosystems and agricultural productivity, but also infrastructure, economic development, and public health. The region's catchments—such as the Camel, Axe, and Somerset Levels and Moors—are ecologically sensitive and already designated as Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) or Ramsar wetland sites. These areas suffer from nutrient overload, reduced water quality, and seasonal fluctuations in water availability. Climate stressors intensify these pre-existing vulnerabilities, challenging regional capacity to maintain ecological integrity while supporting economic growth, particularly in agriculture and housing development.

The Westcountry's adaptation strategy is organized around three interdependent KCS, each facing unique climate-related risks but also presenting leverage points for resilience interventions:

- **Agriculture (80% of land use):** The agricultural sector contributes significantly to nutrient runoff—both point and diffuse source—resulting in pollution and water quality degradation at catchment scale. The sector also faces increasing pressure from droughts and regulatory limits. However, it holds significant potential for improvement through nature-based solutions (NBS) such as improved slurry management, constructed wetlands, and riparian buffers. If appropriately incentivized, these practices can also yield co-benefits in carbon sequestration, biodiversity, and economic returns for farmers through reduced fertilizer costs and participation in ecosystem markets.
- **Water Business Sector (developers, utilities, carbon offset providers):** Water sector actors are constrained by nutrient headroom limits in rivers, which restricts further property development and investment. These constraints are exacerbated by droughts that reduce dilution capacity, intensifying pollution. However, this sector has strong potential to drive systemic transformation through investments in environmental performance linked to offset credits and sustainable water management. Its engagement is crucial for ensuring that catchment-level interventions translate into long-term, regulated planning benefits.
- **River Habitats and Species:** The region's aquatic ecosystems are highly sensitive to hydrological shifts. Flooding exacerbates the transport of nutrients and sediments, while periods of low flow concentrate pollutants. Native biodiversity is under threat, and ecosystem connectivity has been disrupted by historical land-use changes. Restoring floodplains, wetlands, and riparian buffers offers a powerful opportunity to rebuild habitat complexity and strengthen the ecological basis for resilience.

To address these interconnected challenges, the WRT is implementing a portfolio of three integrated solutions that combine technical, ecological, and financial innovation:

- Nature-based solutions (NBS) including Integrated Constructed Wetlands (ICW), sediment trapping features and riparian buffers: ICW involves the deployment of designed wetland systems to intercept agricultural runoff before it enters sensitive waterways. These wetlands are designed to reduce nitrogen and phosphorus loading, stabilize pH, and enhance dissolved oxygen levels. They also contribute to flood control and habitat restoration. By installing these systems in key locations, WRT aims to deliver both compliance with conservation objectives and wider ecosystem benefits. In a similar way sediment trapping features and riparian buffers deployed in strategic places help to trap and slow agricultural run-off including nutrient and sediment.
- Integrated Constructed Wetland Monitoring (ICWM): ICWM provides the performance verification layer necessary for long-term credibility of the ICW installations. It includes sensor networks, real-time data monitoring, and validation tools to ensure accurate tracking of environmental improvements. This system not only informs adaptive management but also underpins the accountability structures required for ecosystem service payments and regulatory reporting.
- Green Bonds (GB): The GB solution is a governance and finance mechanism that links ecosystem service delivery with investor returns. By piloting Phosphate Credit schemes, WRT is establishing pathways for developers and other buyers to finance ecological restoration. The green bond structure ensures that returns are tied to verified outcomes, incentivizing performance across the life cycle of the interventions.

Together, these solutions constitute a systemic resilience strategy. ICW provides physical impact. ICWM delivers the measurement framework to verify that impact. GB builds the governance and financial capacity to scale and sustain it. Crucially, these interventions are not isolated. They are designed to function as a portfolio—each supporting the effectiveness and longevity of the others. Beyond implementation, WRT is also engaging communities through citizen science, fostering bottom-up support and awareness. Participatory approaches help build trust, surface local knowledge, and secure the long-term stewardship necessary for resilient land and water management.

The resilience capacity of the three Westcountry solutions is assessed with bubble size representing the frequency of relevant performance categories and indicators. ICW demonstrated the highest resilience capacity score (4.09), followed by ICWM (4.00) and GB (3.91). The assessed Timespans were two years for ICWM, three years for GB, and ten years for ICW, reflecting differences in solution maturity, durability, and institutional embedding. The following analysis presents each profile, identifying the performance categories and indicators that shape their resilience contributions, confidence levels, and associated uncertainties.

Integrated Constructed Wetlands (ICW)

Summary

ICW achieved a high resilience capacity score of 4.09, reflecting its strong ecological fit with the Westcountry’s key climate challenges—nutrient pollution, flood risk, and biodiversity loss. ICW improves water quality and reduces runoff. Key strengths include high-confidence water quality indicators supported by sensor and lab data, though some uncertainty remains due to seasonal effects and early-stage deployments. With a projected 10-year timespan, ICW’s resilience depends on landowner participation, maintenance, and governance mechanisms like phosphate crediting. Stakeholder engagement is emerging, showing promise but requiring more institutional coordination.

ICW received a resilience capacity score of 4.09, reflecting its strong ecological alignment with the Westcountry’s core climate and water management challenges—specifically nutrient pollution, water quality degradation, and biodiversity loss. Its strength lies in tangible, nature-based interventions that construct wetlands within catchments to intercept nutrient runoff, retain floodwaters, and restore aquatic habitats. These ecosystem functions are pivotal for enhancing the resilience of both agricultural landscapes and aquatic systems. The most influential performance categories in the ICW profile include Water Quality and Risk and Resilience. Within Water Quality, indicators such as reductions in nitrogen and phosphorus loading were rated as highly relevant and achieved maximum Confidence scores. This alignment of central importance and strong evidence signifies high resilience potential. Real-time sensor data and laboratory monitoring further support these findings, though moderate uncertainty remains due to seasonal variability and the early maturity of some installations.

ICW’s estimated operational timespan of 10 years suggests strong durability, underpinned by landowner engagement and public investment. However, sustained impact depends on ongoing maintenance and adaptive governance, including reliable phosphate credit valuation and sediment management. In terms of Stakeholder Engagement, ICW demonstrated moderate Relevance and stronger Confidence, with evidence of community feedback/workshops, and landowner involvement—though often informal or pilot-scale, warranting caution when interpreting institutional depth. Similarly, Management and Coordination revealed strong internal collaboration but varied stakeholder coordination, underscoring the complexity of implementing multi-actor nature-based solutions.

Integrated Constructed Wetland Monitoring (ICWM)

Resilience capacity score: 4 with 2 years Timespan

Summary

ICWM enhances Westcountry’s climate resilience by providing reliable monitoring and verification. It enables trusted data on nutrient reduction and ecological performance, which is crucial for stakeholder confidence. Strong scores in System Performance, Data Quality, and Financial Viability reflect its technical soundness, though operational indicators like sensor maintenance and update cycles reveal infrastructure challenges. Public engagement and private investment added visibility, but with limited long-term certainty. Its two-year timespan supports short-term validation, but sustained resilience impact requires ongoing maintenance, reinvestment, and adaptive management.

ICWM received a resilience capacity score of 4.00, positioning it as a vital enabler within the Westcountry’s climate adaptation strategy. While not directly delivering environmental transformation, ICWM strengthens resilience through robust monitoring, performance verification, and support for adaptive management of ICWs. This solution ensures that nutrient reductions and ecological benefits are not only claimed but quantifiably demonstrated, an essential function for building trust among stakeholders and investors. Key performance categories include System Performance, Data Quality, and Financial Viability. Indicators such as continuous monitoring, sampling validation, and monitoring data accuracy scored 5 in both Relevance and Confidence, highlighting their critical role and evidence base. However, operational sub-indicators—such as sensor maintenance, response efficiency, and software update frequency—showed more moderate Confidence scores, flagging issues related to equipment reliability and support infrastructure.

Stakeholder engagement via citizen science and private investment drew mixed scores. While public participation enhances visibility and legitimacy, its Relevance to system performance is moderate, and its long-term impact depends on program continuity and user training. In Financial Viability, investment and operational indicators scored consistently high, showing promise for cost-effective implementation. The Timespan for ICWM was updated to two years, aligning with typical digital solution cycles and the requirement for at least one year of post-installation monitoring. While this is sufficient for short-term validation, it limits long-term resilience contributions unless extended through continuous updates, sensor lifecycle planning, and stakeholder reinvestment.

Green Bonds (GB)

Summary

GB operates as a governance and financing instrument to catalyze long-term investments in ecological services at the catchment scale. While not delivering direct environmental change, GB facilitates systemic transformation through mechanisms like Phosphate Credits, aligning public and private stakeholders. Its top performance categories include Monitoring and Stakeholder Engagement, supported by indicators such as payment realization and operational cost efficiency. With a three-year timespan reflecting early-stage implementation, GB shows strong relevance and moderate confidence, signaling high potential that depends on sustained policy and market integration.

🔍 GB achieved a resilience capacity score of 3.91, representing a governance and financing mechanism designed to unlock long-term investment in catchment-scale ecological services. Although it does not deliver direct environmental interventions, GB enables scalable transformation by incentivising landowners, aligning policy instruments, and coordinating multi-stakeholder partnerships through instruments like Phosphate Credits. Top scoring performance categories include Monitoring, Evaluation and Adaptation, and Stakeholder Communication. Indicators such as payment realization, ethical broker satisfaction, and setup/operational costs reflect a system in an early stage with strong potential for development and impact. Scores across Relevance and Confidence generally fall within the 3–5 range, indicating perceived importance tempered by implementation uncertainty.

The Timespan for GB has been updated to three years, based on the requirement to monitor outcomes for up to three years post-implementation if the solution aims to support biodiversity credit validation. While this duration aligns with investor reporting cycles and early-stage credit maturation, it is relatively short for a financial mechanism intended to promote long-term landscape change. Longer-term continuity will depend on institutional uptake, market acceptance, and policy integration beyond pilot funding windows.

In synthesis, the three solutions present a well-balanced portfolio that leverages ecological infrastructure (ICW), technological support (ICWM), and institutional financing (GB). ICW delivers the most direct, high-confidence environmental outcomes. ICWM ensures these benefits are reliably monitored and adjusted. GB provides the long-term incentive structures necessary for replication and sustainability. This interdependence is critical: ICW would struggle to scale without GB; GB requires verified outcomes via ICWM; and ICWM depends on deployed interventions like ICW. The complementarity of these solutions

enhances systemic adaptability—no single solution is sufficient, but together they reinforce each other's strengths. While uncertainty persists across technical, perceptual, and regulatory domains, the participatory validation process and structured scoring methodology increase transparency and traceability. These profiles should be interpreted not as static evaluations, but as strategic tools for adaptive learning, targeting investment, and refining future implementation across the Westcountry and beyond.

4.3 Galicia, Spain

The region of Galicia in northwest Spain is ecologically rich but highly exposed to climate-related risks, particularly in its coastal and marine zones. As the source of approximately 40% of the EU's mussel production, aquaculture is a vital sector for the regional economy, employing more than 5,000 people. However, this sector faces intensifying threats from extreme weather events, harmful algal blooms, and changes in water and sediment conditions, all of which undermine infrastructure stability, shellfish productivity, and long-term viability. Clam farms and intertidal shellfish harvesting—largely performed by women—are also at risk due to shifting coastal dynamics.

In response, Galicia has adopted the Galician Climate Change Strategy 2050 and the Integrated Regional Plan for Energy and Climate (2019–2023), which together promote adaptation, mitigation, research, and sustainable governance. Aquaculture is identified as a strategic priority within these plans. Still, local communities often lack access to timely data and face barriers in assessing current capacities and viable adaptation options. The Galician demonstrator aims to build a region-specific, transformational approach for mussel and clam sectors. By deploying digital tools, monitoring systems, and participatory governance mechanisms, the initiative enhances resilience capacity, supports decision-making, and strengthens coordination among institutions, producers, and citizens in the face of growing climate uncertainty.

The region's adaptation strategy targets two interlinked Key Community Systems (KCS):

- **Mussel aquaculture:** Supporting over 5,000 jobs, the sector faces structural damage risks to mussel rafts from storms, seed shortages, and biological stressors such as harmful algal blooms. These risks demand both technological innovation and ecosystem-based monitoring to ensure viability.
- **Clam and shellfish farming on intertidal sandbanks:** With more than 600 coastal farms and 3,500 shellfish gatherers—predominantly women—this sector is vulnerable to changes in sediment structure and coastal hydrodynamics. Habitat loss, productivity decline, and rising mortality rates threaten the social and economic fabric of these coastal communities.

To address these vulnerabilities, the Galician demonstrator is implementing a multi-dimensional adaptation portfolio, combining digital technology, participatory governance, and ecosystem-based monitoring. The three primary solutions are:

- **Resilience Index (RI):** A behavioral change and governance tool co-developed with stakeholders to assess risk scenarios and resilience pathways in aquaculture sectors. It enhances stakeholder participation, scenario planning, and shared understanding of adaptive strategies.
- **Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM):** A technological solution that deploys real-time sensors to monitor environmental conditions and mussel raft performance, supporting adaptive decision-making and climate resilience at the farm level.
- **Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM):** A digital monitoring system tailored to sandbank ecosystems, measuring topographic and bathymetric data, sediment dynamics, and sediment quality parameters to inform long-term planning and community-based adaptation.

Together, these solutions form a systemic adaptation strategy. RI fosters institutional alignment and participatory governance; MRM provides real-time environmental and production insights; and INTERM enables evidence-based management of sediment-sensitive intertidal areas. Each contributes uniquely to building resilience, while reinforcing others through shared data, coordinated planning, and community engagement.

The resilience capacity of the three solutions is assessed with bubble size representing the frequency of relevant performance categories and indicators. RI achieved the highest resilience capacity score at 4.21, followed by MRM at 4.10 and INTERM at 3.60. The estimated timespans were three years for RI, and two years each for MRM and INTERM. The following subsections analyze each solution’s profile in detail, examining the relevance and confidence of performance categories, key indicators, and associated uncertainties.

Resilience Index (RI)

Summary

RI highlights its institutional role in guiding adaptation in the mussel aquaculture sector. It supports behavioral and governance transformation through participatory evaluation and decision-support tools. Strong scores in Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation reflect high relevance and confidence in stakeholder collaboration and roadmap design. With a three-year timespan, RI allows embedding in governance processes, though uncertainties remain around long-term financing and institutional continuity, making sustained facilitation essential for maintaining its transformative potential.

RI received the resilience capacity score of 4.21, emphasizing its strategic importance in fostering behavioral and governance change across the mussel aquaculture sector. Unlike infrastructure or sensor-based tools, RI delivers systemic insight through participatory evaluation, decision-support development, and multi-stakeholder dialogue. It represents an institutional innovation, promoting adaptation culture, gender-sensitive decision-making, and long-term roadmap definition. The most relevant performance category is the Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation. Indicators such as stakeholder collaboration, perception improvement, and roadmap definition scored high in both Relevance (4–5) and Confidence (4–5), signalling well-grounded implementation with cross-sectoral involvement. However, Financial Viability indicators had moderate Confidence scores (3–4), reflecting uncertainties around long-term funding for capacity-building initiatives.

The timespan for RI was estimated at 3 years, allowing adequate time for developing, testing, and embedding the tool in sectoral governance. Still, uncertainties remain in ensuring continuity after external support ends. The solution's reliance on ongoing facilitation and institutional buy-in represents an area for improvement.

Mussel-Raft Monitoring (MRM)

Summary

MRM confirms its role as a strong operational tool for aquaculture adaptation. It supports real-time environmental monitoring and integrates data into management decisions. Key strengths include high relevance and confidence for indicators like data quality and stakeholder data use. However, lower confidence in maintenance-related indicators reflects environmental risks and long-term upkeep needs. Its two-year timespan supports rapid response but limits durability without ongoing investment.

MRM scored 4.10, confirming its role as a robust operational solution supporting data-informed aquaculture adaptation. MRM contributes directly to resilience through sensor-based environmental monitoring and real-time data integration into production management. This digital backbone enhances system responsiveness and supports rapid detection of stress conditions. Key performance categories include Data Quality, Stakeholder Engagement, and Management and Coordination. Indicators such as continuous monitoring, environmental data access, and stakeholder data use scored Relevance and Confidence mostly between 4–5. Nonetheless, indicators related to environmental challenges and maintenance costs showed reduced Confidence (2–3), due to risks like weather-induced sensor errors, and long-term maintenance requirements.

The timespan for MRM is set at 2 years, reflecting typical lifecycles of digital hardware and calibration needs in harsh marine environments. While strong in real-time resilience, the short timespan limits its long-term stability unless sustained by reinvestment and operational support.

Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM)

Summary

INTERM has its role as a specialized monitoring solution supporting climate adaptation. It provides critical sedimentary and spatial data for aquaculture and risk assessment. High scores in sampling and stakeholder collaboration confirm its technical credibility, but limited modelling integration and external partner dependency constrain long-term impact. The 2-year timespan aligns with future resilience that depends on sustained institutional support and improved confidence in translating data into actionable planning outcomes.

🔍 INTERM scored a resilience capacity of 3.60, reflecting its role as a highly specialized but supportive monitoring solution in Galicia’s climate adaptation strategy. The solution focuses on intertidal and sediment dynamics essential for aquaculture viability and ecosystem assessment. It plays a key enabling role by providing spatial, bathymetric, and sedimentary data that supports broader planning and operational decisions across marine and coastal systems. Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation is the dominant performance category. High Relevance and Confidence (mostly 4/4) were recorded for indicators such as sampling requirements, sandbank monitoring completion, strategy scheme readiness. These suggest that INTERM contributes credible, critical data for coastal resilience planning. However, lower Confidence in investment, particularly in morphodynamic modelling, highlights concerns about data coverage, accuracy, and the practical usefulness of outputs for post-implementation decision-making, reflecting ongoing reliance on manual fieldwork and limited integration of modelling tools into operational planning.

Stakeholder Involvement scored highly, highlighting effective collaboration between researchers and shellfish harvesters. Risk and Resilience indicators reflect dependency on external partners, though this is offset by moderate-to-high local involvement. Ongoing value depends on institutional continuity and budget for sensor upkeep.

The three Galician solutions represent a complementary resilience strategy, each contributing distinct but interconnected capacities. RI received the highest resilience capacity score, underscoring its role in strengthening institutional coordination, stakeholder collaboration, and long-term governance planning. Its high relevance and confidence in indicators such as decision-tool perception and stakeholder diversity

illustrate its importance for adaptive capacity building. MRM delivers robust technical performance through continuous environmental monitoring, accurate data collection, and participatory engagement. Its value lies in enabling mussel producers and public actors to make informed, real-time decisions under climate stress. Despite some operational uncertainties—such as maintenance challenges in harsh marine environments—its high confidence in key indicators reinforces its catalytic role. INTERM focuses on intertidal zone monitoring. While its scope is more technical and spatial, it contributes crucial sediment and hydrodynamic data that support both operational planning and ecological forecasting. Its resilience potential is moderated by reliance on external partners and shorter timespan. Together, these solutions address institutional, operational, and ecological dimensions of resilience.

4.4 Oristano, Italy

The coastal area of Oristano, located in western Sardinia, Italy, is an ecologically rich and climatically sensitive region characterized by a mosaic of rivers, lagoons, and salt marshes. These wetlands, covering over 7,700 hectares and representing more than 60% of Sardinia's total wetland area, are protected under the Ramsar Convention and Natura 2000 network. Human activities, including fishing cooperatives, small-scale tourism, and agriculture, are closely interwoven with the region's natural systems, making it a unique socio-ecological landscape. However, Oristano faces multiple climate-related vulnerabilities. Rising sea levels, saltwater intrusion, high nutrient and sediment loads, and increased frequency of extreme weather events (including coastal storms, droughts, and heavy rainfall) are intensifying pressure on ecosystems and infrastructure. These changes threaten wetland biodiversity, reduce ecosystem productivity, and increase risks to water supply and cultural heritage. The aquaculture sector, reliant on stable salinity and water quality, is especially vulnerable.

Two KCS that are central to Oristano's climate adaptation strategy:

- **Water Systems (rivers, lakes, wetlands):** Oristano's extensive wetland complex, including the Marceddì and San Giovanni systems, plays a crucial role in flood regulation, water quality maintenance, and biodiversity support. However, these ecosystems are under mounting stress due to climate-induced droughts, intensive upstream land use, and high nutrient and sediment loading from agriculture, and mining. These pressures result in eutrophication, deteriorating water quality, and the proliferation of invasive species. The impacts are further intensified by the water scarcity of upstream tributaries, which reduces flushing and exacerbates stagnation. Restoring and safeguarding these systems is essential for ecosystem resilience and sustainable resource management.
- **Nature Conservation and Tourism:** Oristano's wetlands, landscapes, and coastal zones offer significant cultural, ecological, and economic value, drawing visitors for birdwatching, eco-tourism, and local artisanal fisheries. These areas are not only biodiversity hotspots but also deeply interwoven with local identity and livelihoods. However, habitat degradation, sea-level rise, and increased frequency of extreme weather events threaten the stability of these ecosystems and the services they provide.

To address these interconnected challenges, Oristano is implementing a portfolio of two integrated solutions that combine participatory governance, nature-based infrastructure, and digital monitoring to strengthen ecological resilience and institutional coordination in its coastal wetland systems:

- **Coastal Contract (COAST):** COAST is a participatory governance initiative for integrated wetland management, reducing fragmentation and enhancing ecological resilience. It promotes stakeholder engagement, raises awareness, and disseminates knowledge through the Local Wetland Observatory (LWO), aiming to support informed decision-making and enable replication of sustainable wetland governance across Oristano and the broader Sardinian region.

- Smart Gate (SG): The SG solution implements NBS with a smart gate and a monitoring system to improve lagoon water circulation and flood regulation. It reduces economic losses, strengthens institutional collaboration, and protects biodiversity. As a scalable model, SG offers a technologically advanced, climate-adaptive approach for wetland restoration in Oristano and beyond.

The COAST initiative emphasizes stakeholder collaboration, institutional coordination, and public awareness through meetings, observatory reporting, and governance toolkits. The SG solution introduces smart infrastructure and a monitoring platform to enhance lagoon-level water regulation and ecosystem health.

COAST received a resilience capacity score of 3.33, and SG scored slightly higher at 3.73. Estimated time horizons are five years for COAST, reflecting governor change cycle, and three years for SG, corresponding to expected technology upgrade cycles. The following sections present individual solution profiles, analyzing the relevance and confidence of their performance categories and indicators, and highlighting associated uncertainties.

Coastal Contract (COAST)

Summary

COAST highlights its role in wetland governance through stakeholder engagement and institutional coordination. Strong relevance and confidence were noted in observatory reporting and contract implementation. However, limited private sector involvement and lower confidence in institutional follow-through reveal challenges in sustaining coordinated action. Its five-year timespan reflects medium-term potential, dependent on continued political and administrative support.

COAST received a resilience capacity score of 3.33, reflecting its role as a governance-led solution aimed at integrating wetland management through participatory mechanisms and institutional coordination. The solution’s strengths lie in formal engagement with public authorities and the deployment of the Local Wetland Observatory, which enhances monitoring and transparency. Indicators related to observatory reporting and contract action achievement were rated highly relevant and generally achieved good confidence scores, suggesting tangible procedural implementation. However, certain dimensions—such as private sector involvement and fulfilment of institutional commitments—showed lower confidence, exposing fragilities in stakeholder follow-through and long-term operational continuity. While initial investment and setup activities were strongly rated, the challenge lies in converting coordinated frameworks into sustained action across institutional and community actors. The estimated timespan of five years supports a medium-term governance outlook, although this depends on consistent political backing and institutional resources.

Smart Gate (SG)

Summary

SG introduces technical performance in managing water flow and flood risk through smart infrastructure. High relevance and confidence in tech-enabled monitoring and sensor maintenance support its operational reliability. Financial indicators, especially cost efficiency, were well rated. However, moderate confidence in institutional coordination and data quality points to governance fragmentation and maintenance dependency. With a three-year timespan, SG's resilience depends on sustained operations and long-term institutional support.

SG, with a resilience capacity score of 3.73, demonstrated stronger performance in technical implementation and operational reliability. It focuses on managing water flow and flood risk through smart infrastructure—providing clear, measurable environmental benefits. High scores in technology-enabled monitoring and sensor maintenance frequency indicate reliable system performance, with less variance in confidence across core indicators. Financial viability indicators, especially maintenance and operational costs, were well scored, confirming the alignment of investment with functional outputs. However, institutional coordination again emerged as a constraint, with relatively low confidence pointing to fragmented leadership or lack of clarity in operational mandates. Data quality indicators, while rated as highly relevant, also showed only moderate confidence due to operational risks and dependency on continuous maintenance. SG is estimated to have a timespan of three years, reflecting the typical durability of technical equipment in coastal conditions. The resilience of this solution depends on the continuity of technical operations, institutional ownership, and capacity to scale. SG offers robust, tangible contributions to environmental resilience but risks becoming siloed if governance and long-term operation support are not addressed in parallel.

Together, COAST and SG represent distinct but potentially synergistic approaches to climate resilience in Oristano. COAST provides the governance framework and participatory structure for integrated wetland management, fostering stakeholder alignment and long-term planning. SG enhances flood regulation and water quality through automated control and monitoring. While developed independently, SG's data outputs could play a valuable role in informing COAST's decision-making processes — offering real-time insights to guide adaptive management. This interplay, though still evolving, illustrates how technical systems can support governance effectiveness. To realize this potential, stronger coordination mechanisms and stable operational support will be essential.

4.5 Guadeloupe, France

Guadeloupe, an overseas region of France in the Caribbean, is highly exposed to climate-related hazards including hurricanes, coastal erosion, floods, droughts, and volcanic activity. Rising temperatures and intensifying extreme weather events—especially more frequent hurricanes and heatwaves—are placing mounting pressure on the island’s ecological systems and infrastructure. These environmental shocks are accompanied by secondary stressors such as land salinization, sargassum invasions, and freshwater scarcity, which together threaten the region’s economy, particularly its tourism and agricultural sectors. Despite having advanced institutional knowledge and ongoing climate vulnerability assessments, Guadeloupe continues to face challenges in implementing effective adaptation actions. Funding constraints, fragmented governance, and limited awareness among local decision-makers have slowed the deployment of targeted solutions.

Guadeloupe’s adaptation strategy is organized around two interdependent Key Community Systems (KCS), each facing distinct climate-related risks while also offering critical leverage points for resilience interventions:

- Agriculture, which contributes 1.5% of Guadeloupe’s GDP and relies heavily on sugarcane and banana monocultures. Climate threats—droughts, floods, and hurricanes—are destabilizing these crops and jeopardizing food sovereignty in a region that imports 80% of its food.
- Tourism, representing 9.5% of GDP and hosting around 850,000 visitors annually, many of whom arrive during hurricane season. Coastal erosion, infrastructure vulnerability, and freshwater stress increasingly affect tourist accommodations and services.

To address these interconnected challenges, Guadeloupe is implementing a portfolio of two integrated solutions that combine behavioral, institutional, and financial innovation:

- Nudging (NUDG): NUDG is a behavioral change intervention using nudging techniques to raise awareness and reduce water and energy consumption among tourists in Guadeloupe. By deploying cognitive design artefacts in hotels, it aims to shift user behavior to critical decision points and support sustainable practices in a climate-vulnerable tourism sector.
- Adaptation Fund (AF): AF is a financial mechanism designed to support municipalities, farmers, and businesses in implementing local climate adaptation projects. By addressing funding gaps and enabling inclusive decision-making, AF promotes long-term resilience planning and institutional alignment in Guadeloupe’s agriculture and tourism sectors.

Together, NUDG and AF constitute a complementary resilience strategy tailored to Guadeloupe’s climate-vulnerable tourism and agriculture sectors. NUDG focuses on behavioral awareness and demand-side adaptation, targeting tourists with nudging tools to promote sustainable water and energy use. AF addresses structural barriers by establishing a financial mechanism to enable locally led adaptation projects, bridging implementation gaps faced by municipalities, farmers, and businesses. While NUDG cultivates individual behavioral shifts, AF builds the governance and funding infrastructure necessary for long-term systemic change. These solutions are not designed in isolation; their effectiveness is enhanced when integrated. Awareness raised through NUDG can build the public support and visibility needed to scale AF investments, while AF can provide resources to institutionalize and expand nudging practices. Together, they represent a layered approach to resilience—combining immediate behavioral engagement with durable financial pathways—grounded in participatory planning and local stakeholder inclusion.

AF received a resilience capacity score of 3.32, while NUDG scored lower at 2.00. The timespans estimated for the solutions were two years for AF and one year for NUDG. The following subsections provide individual analyses of each solution’s profile, including performance category contributions, indicator-level scoring, and key uncertainties related to their implementation.

Nudging (NUDG)

Summary

NUDG is an early-stage behavioral change solution designed to raise awareness and encourage water and energy conservation among tourists in Guadeloupe. Its resilience capacity is limited due to low relevance and confidence across most indicators. The short implementation period, lack of institutional integration, and minimal monitoring infrastructure hinder its ability to deliver sustained impact. While the concept aligns with awareness-raising objectives, weak evidence of behavioral shifts and insufficient stakeholder engagement reduce its systemic value. To become a meaningful resilience intervention, NUDG would require deeper integration with tourism operations, clearer outcome tracking, and institutional support mechanisms.

🔍 NUDG received a resilience capacity score of 2.00, reflecting both its experimental character and early-stage implementation status. The solution aimed to raise awareness among tourists and hotel staff about water and energy consumption and to encourage more sustainable behavior, particularly in shower usage. Despite its potential value for shifting individual consumption patterns, the resilience assessment revealed low relevance across most indicators and limited confidence in the observed outcomes. Key indicators related to behavioral change—such as changes in water consumption and energy use—were assigned only moderate relevance (scores of 2–3), and similarly low confidence (scores of 2). The observed impacts of nudging interventions were difficult to quantify reliably due to the short trial period, inconsistent user feedback, and a lack of baseline or control group comparisons. Additionally, indicators tied to management and coordination, including support responsiveness and implementation effectiveness, scored low in confidence due to limited institutional involvement and uncertain follow-up capacity.

The solution's timespan was estimated at one year, consistent with its pilot nature. However, the absence of supporting institutional structures or long-term monitoring frameworks limits its contribution to systemic resilience. Interpretation of the results suggests that while NUDG shows potential for raising awareness and seeding behavioral change, its current design and deployment do not establish a stable, repeatable function. The limited evidence base, low stakeholder commitment, and short lifecycle contribute to its low resilience capacity score. To improve its relevance, future iterations would require more robust evaluation methods, deeper integration with hospitality sector operations, and stronger alignment with institutional adaptation strategies.

Adaptation Fund (AF)

Summary

AF's resilience profile reveals a promising but still-evolving instrument. It fills a strategic gap in climate finance access, particularly for under-resourced actors, and lays the groundwork for more systemic adaptation investment. However, its ability to maintain performance over time depends on follow-through, multi-level institutional cooperation, and the creation of clear pathways for fund replication. As such, the current score reflects strong potential tempered by the early stage of implementation and structural dependencies still under development.

AF achieved a resilience capacity score of 3.32, designed to close financing gaps for municipalities, farmers, and businesses with local adaptation projects, AF represents a novel approach to devolved climate finance in France. Its phased structure, with a feasibility assessment followed by testing of fund mechanisms, offers a strategic model for inclusive, bottom-up adaptation support. Several performance categories contributed meaningfully to the resilience score. Governance-related indicators such as public organization conversion and governance structure flexibility were rated highly in both relevance and confidence (scores of 4–5), demonstrating a solid institutional framework and adaptability of the funding mechanism. Private sector engagement, while included, scored lower in confidence (2), pointing to persistent challenges in mobilizing private capital or aligning incentives across sectors.

AF's operational design scored moderately across financial viability and risk categories. Indicators such as fund financing viability and public-private project alignment confirmed confidence in the fund's basic functionality, but also revealed sensitivity to long-term financial sustainability and institutional coordination. The two-year timespan reflects the projected period needed to demonstrate feasibility and prepare for replication or scaling, though this remains conditional on stakeholder buy-in and successful pilot execution.

NUDG and AF reveals a strategically layered but uneven portfolio. AF demonstrates a relatively high resilience capacity (3.32), driven by strong relevance in governance and financial indicators, such as public organization engagement, governance structure flexibility, and public-private project alignment. Its two-year timespan reflects early-stage maturity but promising potential, especially if institutional commitment and fund viability are strengthened. In contrast, NUDG scores notably lower, primarily due to its experimental nature, limited timespan (one year), and reliance on unvalidated behavioral

indicators. While its intent to influence tourist water consumption is relevant, low confidence levels and underdeveloped monitoring mechanisms constrain its resilience impact. The analysis highlights that AF acts as the structural enabler of long-term resilience, while NUDG serves as a testbed for behavioral innovation. Their combined value lies in addressing both system-level financing gaps and social engagement needs. However, to function effectively as a cohesive adaptation strategy, integration must be deepened, by aligning behavioral insights with financial instruments, extending NUDG's operational life, and enhancing AF's support for social experimentation. Uncertainty remains high due to implementation constraints and limited data, but the participatory scoring process offers a foundation for adaptive learning and scaling.

4.6 Egaleo, Greece

Egaleo, a densely built municipality within the Athens metropolitan area, faces a convergence of climate and socio-economic challenges. The city is increasingly vulnerable to extreme heat, heavy precipitation, flooding, and thunderstorms, with wildfires in Baroutadiko Grove posing a persistent seasonal threat. Urban flash floods, aggravated by the nearby Kifissos River and insufficient stormwater systems, have repeatedly damaged infrastructure and homes. The urban heat island effect, coupled with poor air quality and minimal green spaces, intensifies public health risks, especially for socially vulnerable groups. High unemployment, low birth rates, and ageing infrastructure further constrain Egaleo's resilience.

Despite these challenges, Egaleo is actively enhancing its adaptive capacity through its participation in the Covenant of Mayors and ongoing revision of its Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP). The TransformAR demonstrator builds on these efforts, implementing a suite of five integrated solutions to address climate vulnerability in three KCS:

- Health – Rapid urbanization and climate stress have worsened air pollution and heat-related risks. Vulnerable populations, including seniors and low-income groups, face increased exposure and limited access to adaptation support.
- Infrastructure – Much of Egaleo's built environment is not climate-resilient. Rising temperatures and storm intensity are accelerating the degradation of roads, drainage, and energy infrastructure.
- Urban Planning – Conventional planning practices have amplified impermeable surface coverage and decreased adaptive capacity. Climate change reinforces urban overheating and overwhelms drainage systems, necessitating innovative planning for climate-responsive development.

To address these systemic challenges, Egaleo is deploying a portfolio of five integrated solutions combining digital tools, public engagement, innovation ecosystems, and evidence-based decision-making:

- Awareness-Raising Modules (AWAR): AWAR delivers structured climate education through workshops, trainings, and co-designed materials tailored to students and educators. It focuses on equipping youth with critical climate knowledge and fostering early-stage behavioral shifts that can ripple through families and communities.
- Citizen App Egaleo (CAE): CAE functions as an interactive digital tool allowing residents to access real-time microclimatic data, submit feedback, and participate in climate-related decision-making processes. It bridges the gap between institutional data and public understanding, turning users into active climate stakeholders.
- Climate Innovation Hub (CIH): CIH acts as a collaborative platform for nurturing climate-resilient entrepreneurship. It provides training, networking opportunities, and operational support for green start-ups, with a strong emphasis on integrating local needs and fostering inclusive innovation ecosystems.

- Demand Analysis for Social Services /Infrastructure (DSI): DSI compiles and analyzes data on health vulnerabilities and social service needs under climate stress. It informs planners and policymakers by revealing service delivery gaps and enabling more equitable, targeted adaptation strategies in Egaleo’s urban environment.
- Smart Climate Stations (SCS): SCS are sensor-based systems installed at municipal sites, capturing hyper-local climate metrics such as temperature, humidity, and air quality. This granular data supports early warning, infrastructure design, and policy responses to heatwaves and flooding.

Together, these five solutions form a layered resilience strategy that integrates educational outreach, digital engagement, economic innovation, vulnerability assessment, and environmental monitoring. AWAR initiates climate literacy and behavioral change, while CAE facilitates continuous civic involvement. CIH converts awareness into economic opportunity, supporting adaptive entrepreneurship. DSI grounds all efforts in spatial and demographic insights, ensuring no community segment is left behind. SCS undergirds the system with real-time climate intelligence, closing the loop between data, decision-making, and public action. Collectively, they position Egaleo to address climate risks with a participatory, evidence-based, and future-oriented framework.

The resilience capacity scores for the solutions are AWAR (3.85), CAE (4.18), CIH (3.98), DSI (3.95), and SCS (4.65). The estimated timespans range from 1 to 4 years, depending on the solution’s maturity and operational scope. The following subsections present detailed profiles for each solution, examining performance categories, indicator-level results, and key uncertainties influencing their resilience contributions.

Awareness-raising Modules (AWAR)

Summary

AWAR reflects strong engagement with schools and youth. High participation and satisfaction in workshops and training indicate a solid educational foundation. However, financial constraints and coordination challenges may limit scale and longevity. The solution’s effectiveness depends on continued institutional backing and integration into curricula. AWAR builds social capital for climate action, embedding long-term awareness and behavioral change, particularly among the younger generation.

AWAR received a resilience capacity score of 3.85. This solution focuses on embedding climate literacy among students, leveraging structured school-based programs to foster early awareness and behavioral change. Performance categories linked to Stakeholder Engagement—such as workshop and training participation—scored high in both relevance and confidence (mostly 4s and 5s), indicating strong institutional support and student receptivity. The design of educational material and youth engagement innovation were also recognized for their strategic role in shaping long-term resilience.

Financial viability, however, showed mixed results. While investment cost efficiency received perfect marks, the actual investment score was low, pointing to resource constraints that may hinder scalability. Additionally, indicators assessing coordination and partner dependency registered moderate confidence scores, emphasizing the importance of cross-stakeholder collaboration for sustained implementation. AWAR’s profile reveals a socially rooted, capacity-building intervention that bridges knowledge gaps but depends on institutional continuity and education system integration for scale and durability.

Citizen App Egaleo (CAE)

Summary

CAE highlights its strong performance as a participatory digital solution for climate communication and civic engagement in Egaleo. CAE enables residents to access and interpret microclimate data. High scores in Risk and Resilience and Financial Viability, especially on local control, data hosting, and operational cost-efficiency, indicate strong alignment with long-term sustainability and user trust. However, gaps emerged in participatory satisfaction, where indicators such as survey, meeting engagement, app utilization scored lower in Confidence. With a one-year timespan, sustained impact will depend on continuous user engagement, feedback integration, and institutional support.

CAE achieved a strong resilience capacity score of 4.18, reflecting its effectiveness as a participatory tool for climate data communication and stakeholder engagement in Egaleo. Operating in synergy with Smart Climate Stations (SCS), CAE translates technical data into accessible insights for public use. The solution excelled in the Risk and Resilience and Financial Viability categories—particularly local control, data hosting, and cost efficiency indicators—all receiving perfect scores, signalling trustworthiness, sustainability, and alignment with long-term data sovereignty. However, some limitations emerged in the participatory aspects. While meeting attendance scored high, other engagement indicators—such as survey participation—revealed a gap between uptake and low confidence in user satisfaction. This points to potential challenges in communication design, feedback quality, or perceived value, which could hinder sustained civic involvement. Similarly, meeting engagement satisfaction scored only 3/2, suggesting that dialogue quality may not match participation levels.

From a monitoring perspective, core indicators like app utilization rate and usability satisfaction performed strongly in relevance, yet Confidence in satisfaction remained low, indicating uncertainty about the depth of user engagement and long-term functionality. With a short Timespan of one year, CAE demonstrates high short-term reliability, but sustaining its impact will require continuous user support, iterative improvement, and institutional commitment.

Climate Innovation Hub (CIH)

Summary

CIH reflects its strength as a catalyst for socio-economic transformation and climate-smart entrepreneurship in Egaleo. The Hub performed best in Stakeholder Engagement, with high scores in participation and training indicators, confirming strong local interest. However, Confidence regarding satisfaction with the events, training quality and feedback was mixed, revealing areas for improvement. While CIH successfully drives behavioral change and collaboration, low scores in political support highlight risks to long-term continuity.

CIH achieved a resilience capacity score of 3.98, positioning it as a promising enabler of socio-economic transformation within Egaleo's adaptation strategy. Designed to foster green entrepreneurship, CIH engages local stakeholders through workshops, training, and participatory innovation. Stakeholder Engagement and Participation emerged as the solution's strongest domain, particularly in terms of workshop attendance, event participation, and training engagement in both relevance and confidence, confirming a strong foundation of interest and mobilization. However, satisfaction scores for events, training, and feedback submission were more mixed (ranging from 2.0 to 4.0), suggesting opportunities to strengthen participant experience and follow-up mechanisms. In Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation, the behavioral change satisfaction indicator scored a perfect in both relevance and confidence, underlining CIH's capacity to catalyse meaningful shifts in sustainable practice and environmental awareness. Stakeholder collaboration also scored well, reflecting the Hub's ability to bridge public, private, and civic actors. Nonetheless, Risk and Resilience indicators such as political and administrative support received notably low marks (2.0/1.0), pointing to institutional fragility that could jeopardize the initiative's longevity.

With a four-year timespan, CIH demonstrates a solid operational base but reveals critical dependencies on stable governance and deeper integration with local values and capacities. Overall, it offers a resilient model for inclusive climate innovation, contingent on improved feedback mechanisms and stronger institutional anchoring.

Demand Analysis for Social Services /Infrastructure (DSI)

Summary

DSI serves as a data-driven tool for assessing health and infrastructure vulnerabilities in Egaleo. Strongest in Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation on the impact of mortality, air pollution, and data reliability. Engagement and cooperation also rated high, while confidence in anticipating unpredictable climate impacts was low. With a one-year timespan, DSI provides valuable insights for short-term planning but depends on institutional commitment and continuous data flows for sustained, long-term resilience impact.

 DSI achieved a resilience capacity score of 3.95, ranking among Egaleo’s most analytically grounded solutions. Focused on identifying service and infrastructure vulnerabilities, particularly in health, it provides essential data for guiding climate-responsive urban planning. The solution performed strongest in Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation. Indicators such as mortality rate, health impacts of air pollution, and data reliability all scored 4–5 in both relevance and confidence, validating DSI’s utility in measuring and mapping public health risks under climate pressure. In Financial Viability, investment-related indicators received moderate-to-high scores (3–4), supporting the cost-efficiency of the analysis process. However, key concerns emerged under Risk and Resilience. Despite strong stakeholder cooperation (5/5), the capacity to anticipate unpredictable climate impacts received a very low confidence score (1), revealing uncertainty in long-term responsiveness. Moderate scores for organizational perception and decision-making potential indicate a need for stronger institutional alignment.

With a short Timespan of one year, DSI offers high immediate value for baseline assessments and policy targeting. To maintain its relevance, however, its findings must feed into iterative planning processes, supported by ongoing data updates, cross-sectoral collaboration, and adaptive governance mechanisms.

Smart Climate Stations (SCS)

Summary

SCS establishes itself as a core enabler of climate intelligence. It offers continuous microclimatic monitoring, feeding real-time data into other solutions like CAE and DSI. System uptime, response efficiency, and data accuracy scored well in relevance and confidence. While maintenance and operational cost efficiency indicators revealed moderate confidence, overall technical performance was consistently strong. With a two-year timespan, SCS provides a reliable foundation for adaptive planning, contingent on sustained investment and upkeep.

SCS recorded the highest resilience capacity score among Egaleo’s five solutions, with a robust 4.65. Designed to deliver continuous microclimatic monitoring, SCS enables data-informed decision-making across municipal functions while feeding critical insights into other solutions like CAE and DSI. It performed exceptionally in System Performance and Data Quality, where indicators such as system uptime, response efficiency, and data accuracy all scored a full 5 in both relevance and confidence—underscoring its technical maturity and centrality in Egaleo’s climate intelligence ecosystem. Monitoring coverage and efficiency also achieved perfect scores, validating the solution’s ability to deliver reliable environmental sensing across a broad area. However, while indicators like computing power and use of energy were considered less relevant to the assessment scope, they still received high confidence ratings, suggesting technical soundness despite limited emphasis. Sensor lifespan satisfaction and maintenance frequency showed more moderate confidence (3), pointing to routine wear and the need for operational planning.

Financial viability presented a mixed picture: while investment cost efficiency was rated high, maintenance and operational cost efficiency revealed potential sustainability concerns due to relatively low relevance and moderate confidence. A two-year timespan was assigned, consistent with expected hardware durability and calibration cycles. Overall, SCS offers a strong, data-driven backbone for Egaleo’s climate adaptation—dependable in the short-to-medium term, with long-term impact reliant on stable financing and maintenance strategies.

Egaleo’s portfolio demonstrates a cohesive and complementary resilience strategy, combining digital monitoring (SCS), civic engagement (CAE), educational outreach (AWAR), innovation infrastructure (CIH), and data-driven planning (DSI). Together, they cover the full spectrum from immediate climate awareness to long-term institutional preparedness. SCS anchors the ecosystem by generating reliable

data. CAE ensures this information reaches and empowers the public. AWAR cultivates behavioral and cultural change from the ground up. CIH accelerates the transition to green practices through entrepreneurship, while DSI turns raw data into actionable planning insights. Importantly, the synergy across solutions enhances their collective value. For example, AWAR and CIH build the social capital that reinforces CAE participation, while DSI and SCS together improve precision in adaptation targeting. This layered approach helps Egaleo address both acute risks (e.g., heatwaves, floods) and chronic vulnerabilities (e.g., poor infrastructure, weak awareness). However, long-term resilience will hinge on continued institutional support, policy alignment, and funding continuity. Strengthening governance and sustaining stakeholder engagement will be crucial for maintaining momentum and scaling successful interventions.

4.7 Cross-demonstrator synthesis

This section synthesizes performance insights within and across solution categories to identify strengths, gaps, and resilience-building opportunities. By examining both category-specific patterns and general trends, the analysis supports more informed, adaptive implementation of climate solutions and highlights areas where methodological refinement and targeted actions can strengthen systemic resilience.

4.7.1 Solution category-specific patterns

To ensure systemic resilience across the TransformAr demonstrators, it is essential to understand the specific performance dynamics of each major solution category. A solution category-specific analysis of performance data helps identify strengths, evidence gaps, and opportunities for improvement, offering insights into how performance metrics are being interpreted and applied across contexts. This analysis aims to clarify which performance categories are most relevant to each solution type, how confident evaluators are in assessing those dimensions, and what kinds of actions are needed to enhance the resilience potential of each category. By examining resilience capacity scores alongside relevance and confidence ratings, this section enables a comparative understanding of where different solution types demonstrate strong performance (category), where measurement reliability varies, and how implementation can be made more robust, adaptive, and context sensitive.

Table 4.1 presents average Relevance (R), Confidence (C), and the number of Indicators (I) used across performance categories for the five main types of adaptation solutions: BCAR, GS, NBS, TDS, and IFE.

Table 4.1 Relevance and confidence of performance by solution category

Solution category *	BCAR			GS			NBS			TDS			IFE		
	R	C	I	R	C	I	R	C	I	R	C	I	R	C	I
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	3,69	3,31	13	4,21	4,29	14				3,36	4,11	14	4,00	4,00	8
Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	3,67	3,25	12	4,00	4,00	10	3,40	4,00	5	3,67	4,33	9	4,50	3,75	4
Financial Viability	4,11	4,33	9	3,80	4,00	5	5,00	4,20	5	3,44	3,94	16	3,00	4,00	2
Risk and Resilience	4,00	4,14	7	4,00	2,60	6	4,83	4,17	6	3,00	3,92	6	4,25	3,63	4
System Performance							4,33	4,17	3	3,76	3,71	25			
Management and Coordination	3,00	3,50	4	4,80	3,20	5	4,00	4,00	8	4,00	4,57	7	4,00	4,00	2
Data Quality							5,00	3,00	2	4,58	4,33	12			
Water Quality							5,00	5,00	6						
Flood Vulnerability							4,80	4,80	5						
Environmental Impact							3,33	4,00	3						
Readiness and Feasibility							5,00	3,00	1				4,00	3,00	2
Governance and Policy													3,50	3,50	2
Biodiversity and Habitat							2,00	4,00	1						
Livability and Comfort							2,00	2,00	1						

* Behavioural change and awareness-raising (BCAR), Governance Schemes (GS), Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), Technological and Digital Solutions (TDS), and Insurance, financial and economic schemes (IFE). R - average of Relevance score, C - average of Confidence score, and I - number of indicators selected.

BCAR solutions aim to shift behaviors, increase awareness, and promote low-tech, people-centric adaptation measures. These often involve apps, campaigns, nudges, and participatory activities. BCAR solutions tend to be people-focused and low-tech, relying heavily on engagement and digital communication tools. These solutions scored highly in Financial Viability (R=4.11, C=4.33), particularly where investment and maintenance costs were easily tracked and minimized, such as in the CAF app, which featured indicators like investment cost efficiency and operational cost (both rated 5 for both relevance and confidence). Strong scores also emerged in Risk and Resilience (R=4.00, C=4.14), especially through indicators like local control, data accessibility, and partner dependency. CAF achieved a high resilience capacity score of 4.74. However, confidence was more limited in Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation (C=3.31) and Stakeholder Engagement (C=3.25), even though these areas are core to behavioural solutions. For example, while CAF tracked app utilization and event attendance well, indicators such as feedback implementation and integration capacity faced challenges in consistent application or documentation. NUDG exhibited variable confidence and relevance in behavioral impact indicators (e.g., change in shower duration, R=3, C=3), highlighting the need for more rigorous participatory monitoring systems and behavioral-tracking methods. These findings suggest that while BCAR solutions are conceptually strong and cost-efficient, their resilience could be further enhanced through more consistent monitoring practices and deeper engagement with end users.

How to enhance the resilience capacity of BCAR

To ensure more reliable and scalable impact measurement in BCAR solutions, the following improvements can help build evidence for change attribution and improve the credibility of behavioural solutions:

- Enhance the reliability of behavioral impact measurement tools.
- Invest in more effective participatory data collection methods, including digital surveys, gamification, and embedded reporting in apps.
- Train local stakeholders or community leaders as data collectors or observers.
- Apply mixed-method approaches, combining quantitative app data with qualitative interviews or diaries.
- Collaborate with behavioral scientists to design longitudinal tracking frameworks.

GS solutions emphasize institutional processes, coordination mechanisms, and regulatory or planning instruments to enhance adaptive capacity. They consistently report high relevance in categories like Management and Coordination (R=4.80) and Monitoring and Evaluation (R=4.21), but often suffer from lower confidence in areas such as Risk and Resilience (C=2.60). This suggests conceptual robustness without equivalent implementation evidence. Key indicators such as Stakeholder Collaboration Impact, and Institutional Coordination score highly in relevance but show uneven confidence due to limited data or incomplete implementation. For example, the solution RI demonstrates high scores in "decision-tool perception improvement" (R=5, C=5) and "stakeholder collaboration impact" (R=4, C=5). In the COAST solution, relevant indicators such as Contract Action Achievement and Stakeholder Coordination were scored highly in relevance (R=5) but had lower confidence (C=3), indicating difficulties in consistent application or evidence availability. Moreover, Commitment Fulfillment scored notably lower in confidence (C=2), highlighting that while institutional structures may exist, evaluators may struggle to confirm their effectiveness or follow-through. This points to a need for clearer operational definitions, stronger documentation practices, and enhanced training in the implementation and evaluation of governance metrics. In general, the average resilience capacity of GS solutions falls slightly behind other categories, with values typically around 3.74 to 3.95. To improve GS solution resilience, it is essential to

refine the definitions and contextual applicability of governance indicators to transform conceptual strength into measurable outcomes, reinforcing the institutional dimension of resilience.

How to enhance the resilience capacity of GS

To improve GS solution resilience, the focus should shift from conceptual planning to the operationalization of governance frameworks. The following actions supports to translate well-structured governance strategies into visible, trackable institutional practices that build long-term resilience:

- Institutionalize regular implementation tracking to bridge the gap between planning and delivery.
- Develop shared documentation protocols and monitoring frameworks to ensure consistent reporting.
- Create digital repositories for knowledge management and ensure personnel continuity.
- Use participatory scorecards and peer reviews to reflect on governance processes.
- Clarify indicator guidelines and provide evaluator training to improve consistency and reduce ambiguity.

NBS include ecosystem-based approaches like green infrastructure, wetlands, and vegetated systems that deliver both climate adaptation and co-benefits. These solutions stand out across almost all categories for both relevance and confidence. For example, in the URB solution, indicators such as Reduction in Nitrogen/Phosphorus, Peak Flow Reduction, and Runoff Reduction score a consistent 5.0 for both relevance and confidence under Water Quality and Flood Vulnerability. Even less direct performance areas such as Risk and Resilience or System Performance exceed 4.0. URB also demonstrated the highest overall resilience capacity score at 4.75. Confidence dips slightly in Data Quality (C=3.00), due to reliance on proxy measurements or lack of real-time sampling. Lower relevance is observed in categories like Biodiversity and Habitat (R=2.00) and Livability and Comfort (R=2.00), which may be harder to quantify or demonstrate over short implementation periods. Despite these minor weaknesses, NBS remains the highest performing solution category overall, with clear strengths in measurable environmental impacts, particularly in the domains of water quality, stormwater management, and nutrient loading reduction. To maximize their resilience potential, NBS should strengthen post-implementation monitoring and expand the types of co-benefits tracked and reinforce the social dimensions of nature-based resilience.

How to enhance the resilience capacity of NBS

To further unlock the potential of NBS, the following actions will help demonstrate the multi-dimensional benefits of NBS, supporting broader adoption and long-term integration into climate strategies:

- Strengthen post-implementation monitoring using low-cost sensors, community science, and environmental audits.
- Expand performance tracking to co-benefits such as public satisfaction, aesthetics, and biodiversity recovery.
- Use participatory assessment tools to capture perception-based indicators.
- Coordinate with academic institutions for long-term ecological monitoring.

TDS include sensing platforms, simulation models, monitoring networks, and data systems that enable precision adaptation. TDS solutions demonstrate a broad and balanced use of performance categories. Relevance scores generally range between 3.4 and 4.0, with high confidence values in Stakeholder Engagement (C=4.33), Management and Coordination (C=4.57), and Data Quality (C=4.33). For instance, the SCS solution in Egaleo illustrates outstanding performance with a resilience score of 4.65 and detailed indicators such as Sensor Uptime, System Response, and Data Accuracy. Despite strong scores in system reliability and data collection, average confidence is somewhat lower in Risk and Resilience (C=3.92), with concerns about data privacy, partner dependency, and systemic risks (e.g., cloud outages). In some cases, cost-related indicators received variable ratings, highlighting uncertainty in long-term financial predictability, especially when business models or cost-saving mechanisms were not well defined. To improve resilience, TDS should prioritize technological redundancy, enhance transparency in supplier and data infrastructure partnerships, and increase user training on emergency protocols.

How to enhance the resilience capacity of TDS

To improve TDS solution resilience, efforts shall focus on strengthening the long-term resilience and scalability to ensure digital tools support not just technical monitoring, but systemic resilience and stakeholder trust.

- Prioritize redundant infrastructure and localized control to mitigate dependency risks.
- Strengthen data governance protocols to ensure privacy, security, and transparency.
- Invest in cost-benefit modeling and clarify value propositions for technical investments.
- Broaden system usability to ensure engagement across diverse users, from public agencies to community stakeholders.
- Link TDS outcomes with decision-making frameworks to support adaptive urban and ecological planning.

IFE solutions address adaptation through funds, credits, subsidies, or financial instruments, often targeting private-sector involvement and landowners. These solutions typically engage fewer indicators but apply them with focused intent. Stakeholder Engagement (R=4.50, C=3.75) and Risk and Resilience (R=4.25, C=3.63) are among the highest-scoring categories, especially in indicators like private-sector investment, conservation covenants, and fund viability. Financial Viability (R=3.00) shows relatively low relevance, possibly due to the experimental or early-stage nature of the financial models. The resilience capacity scores for IFE solutions such as AF and CEI range from 3.32 to 3.91, suggesting room for improvement in both the scope and depth of impact. Indicator confidence across categories is modest, pointing to limited data consistency or comparability, particularly in areas where financial innovation is recent and evolving.

How to enhance the resilience capacity of IFE

To elevate the resilience impact and evidence base of IFE, actions shall ensure that financial innovation is grounded in robust data and institutional frameworks, enabling effective climate resilience financing.

- Strengthen data systems to better capture financial and socio-ecological returns on investment.
- Standardize metrics for risk-sharing, cost-effectiveness, and financial governance.
- Foster partnerships with financial institutions to align adaptation finance with market logic.
- Develop robust M&E tools for assessing long-term fund performance and stakeholder satisfaction.
- Expand training and outreach to improve awareness of financial adaptation mechanisms.

The analysis of solution categories reveals distinct strengths and strategic gaps. Tangible, physical-risk-oriented performance categories—such as Water Quality, Flood Vulnerability, and System Performance—consistently score the highest in both relevance and confidence, especially within NBS and TDS solutions. These areas benefit from well-established monitoring protocols, clear impact pathways, and measurable outcomes, contributing to high resilience capacity scores such as URB (4.75) and SCS (4.65). In contrast, “softer” domains like Livability and Comfort, Governance and Policy, and Readiness and Feasibility remain underdeveloped. These areas either lack standard frameworks or are inconsistently applied across demonstrators. For example, while GS report high relevance in institutional indicators, they suffer from lower confidence—suggesting a conceptual but untested capacity. Similarly, BCAR and IFE solutions show strong cost-efficiency and stakeholder engagement potential in resilience capacity but face challenges in impact verification and long-term monitoring. The confidence score emerges as a key proxy for the maturity of monitoring systems and the reliability of reported impact. High-confidence indicators (e.g., nutrient reduction, data accuracy, stakeholder satisfaction) not only strengthen the credibility of solutions but also inform learning loops and adaptive management. Solutions with high relevance but low confidence highlight areas where intervention design is promising, but implementation evidence is missing or weak.

To address these gaps, each solution type benefits from targeted actions, as outlined in the “How to enhance the resilience capacity”. These recommendations reflect the TransformAr experience and should be treated as context-sensitive guidance—not universal prescriptions. Methodological refinements, including clearer indicator definitions, evaluator support, and stakeholder co-design, are essential to improve relevance and confidence scores in future assessments.

Ultimately, enhancing resilience across solution types requires a multi-pronged strategy: 1) Invest in robust, user-friendly monitoring frameworks; 2) Diversify metrics to include both tangible impacts and qualitative co-benefits; 3) Foster cross-sector collaboration to bridge governance, financial, and technical divides. These insights enable not only improved assessment in future TransformAr cycles, but also support scaling adaptive solutions across European regions with greater confidence, equity, and effectiveness.

4.7.2 Cross-Solution Trends and Insights

Performance categories across all solutions were evaluated based on their average relevance, confidence scores, and frequency of application (indicator count), as illustrated in Figure 4.1. This general analysis investigates cross-cutting trends in how different performance categories are used and perceived across adaptation solutions. The aim is to uncover shared strengths, recurring gaps, and areas requiring methodological reinforcement. By identifying which categories are most central, which are context-dependent, and which remain underutilized, the analysis supports the development of more balanced, comprehensive, and resilient adaptation strategies. These insights inform general recommendations to enhance the quality, consistency, and inclusivity of resilience assessments across diverse solution types.

Figure 4.1 Relevance and confidence of performance across all solutions

Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation is the most frequently applied category (49 indicators), with consistent relevance (3.80) and confidence (3.93). Its prominence highlights the central role of adaptive management and learning in resilience-building across diverse contexts. Examples include indicators such as system uptime rate, usability satisfaction, stakeholder feedback implementation, and environmental data access. These reflect a strong integration of digital monitoring tools, community interaction, and evidence-based adaptation planning. Stakeholder Engagement and Participation also demonstrates broad adoption (40 indicators), with balanced relevance and confidence scores (3.80/3.83). Indicators like event attendance rate, feedback satisfaction, meeting participation, and training effectiveness highlight its importance for inclusive governance and participatory resilience planning. Financial Viability (37 indicators) is another core pillar, with a slightly higher average confidence (4.08), likely reflecting the more tangible and quantifiable nature of economic data. Common indicators include investment cost efficiency, maintenance cost, and business model economic risk. Their application demonstrates strong alignment with financial accountability and long-term viability.

Water Quality, Flood Vulnerability, and Data Quality exhibit the highest scores in both relevance and confidence despite their lower application frequency. Water Quality (5.00/5.00, 6 indicators) is assessed through indicators like reduction in nitrogen and phosphorus loading, improvement in pH and dissolved oxygen levels, and reduction in heavy metal concentration. These indicators are particularly used in nature-based solutions aimed at improving ecological conditions. Flood Vulnerability (4.80/4.80, 5 indicators) includes indicators such as peak flow reduction, flood hazard mitigation, and damage reduction—directly linked to infrastructural resilience and ecosystem service enhancement. Data Quality (4.64/4.14, 14 indicators), typically found in technological solutions, uses indicators like continuous monitoring, sensor coverage redundancy, and data accuracy validation to ensure robust information flow in resilience operations.

Readiness and Feasibility (4.33/3.00, 3 indicators) demonstrates high relevance but relatively lower confidence. Indicators such as sectoral readiness, stakeholder adoption readiness, and method applicability are seen as critical but often rely on subjective expert judgment, short timelines, or lack longitudinal data. Risk and Resilience (4.00/3.75, 29 indicators) displays a similar pattern, where indicators like partner dependency, cloud data capacity, and local control and ownership are acknowledged as essential but present challenges in cross-demonstrator standardization. Management and Coordination (4.00/3.92, 26 indicators) also reflects this, especially with indicators such as institutional coordination, engagement strategies, and internal communication effectiveness, which are inherently influenced by local context.

Environmental Impact (3.33/4.00, 3 indicators) and Biodiversity and Habitat (2.00/4.00, 1 indicator) reflect lower relevance but high confidence. For Environmental Impact, indicators are drawn from LCA metrics such as freshwater eutrophication, resource use, and climate impact, providing technically robust results even if they are not mainstreamed in resilience planning. Biodiversity and Habitat relies on tools like the NSC-BM model to evaluate species richness and habitat health, although its application remains niche due to the complexity and specificity of ecological modeling.

Livability and Comfort (2.00/2.00, 1 indicator) and Governance and Policy (3.50/3.50, 2 indicators) score lowest in both dimensions. The former includes indicators such as increased green space and aesthetic appreciation, which are valuable but often lack robust data or standardized methods. The latter includes flexible financing models and action plan clarity—conceptually vital but difficult to measure consistently across cases due to governance diversity and limited operational indicators.

In general, categories can broadly be clustered into three functional groups based on the nature of their contributions and patterns of use:

- Core functional pillars: Monitoring, Evaluation, Adaptation, Financial Viability, and Stakeholder Engagement and Participation together form the core functional pillars of the TransformAr framework. Their widespread usage and methodological maturity provide a strong base for adaptive and inclusive resilience strategies.
- Category-specific enablers: Water Quality, Flood Vulnerability, Data Quality, Risk and Resilience, System Performance, and Management and Coordination function as solution category-specific enablers. Their strong relevance and variable confidence reflect their importance in targeted applications, such as stormwater management, digital infrastructure, or urban governance.
- Emerging or underrepresented dimensions: Environmental Impact, Readiness and Feasibility, Governance and Policy, Livability and Comfort, and Biodiversity and Habitat comprise the cluster of emerging or underrepresented dimensions. These areas require methodological refinement and broader application to enhance comprehensiveness and social inclusivity.

Altogether, the functional groupings can inform both strategic prioritization and methodological refinement in future resilience assessments. They allow practitioners to differentiate between what must be included across all solutions, what should be emphasized in context-specific interventions, and what requires further conceptual and technical development. This approach enables TransformAr and other adaptation efforts to become more inclusive, evidence-based, and context-sensitive, ensuring that resilience planning is both robust and adaptive to diverse real-world challenges.

5 Conclusion

5.1 Summary

This report serves as a practical guide for applying the Sustainability Rating Method (SRM) to assess the resilience capacity of climate adaptation solutions. It builds on real-world examples from six TransformAr demonstrators and aims to support both reflection and replication. The main purpose is not to rank solutions but rather to help stakeholders—project planners, evaluators, funders, and policymakers—identify how different adaptation strategies contribute to systemic resilience, how to structure meaningful assessments, and how to interpret complex data in transparent and actionable ways.

The findings below summarize key patterns observed across demonstrators, offering lessons for future adaptation planning and assessment efforts.

- Solutions function best in interconnected portfolios.

A recurring insight from the demonstrators is that resilience does not arise from any single solution. Rather, it emerges through portfolios where monitoring (e.g. SCS), governance (e.g. COAST, AF), and physical interventions (e.g. ICW, NBS) work together. Designing for complementarity—rather than isolated pilots—is key. This guide provides examples of such integration and highlights how SRM can track the added value of systemic design.

- Indicator co-definition and scoring foster local ownership.

Co-designing indicators with local stakeholders improved both the credibility of results and their utility. Participatory scoring sessions helped demonstrators reflect on strengths and gaps, while enhancing their internal capacity for future evaluation. SRM thus functions as both a technical method and a facilitation tool, translating local knowledge into structured, comparable insights.

- Certain categories are consistently prioritized, while others need further development.

Performance categories like Monitoring, Evaluation and Adaptation, Financial Viability, and Stakeholder Engagement were most frequently used and scored with moderate-to-high confidence. Conversely, Governance and Policy, Livability and Comfort, and Biodiversity and Habitat were less frequently applied or had mixed relevance. This suggests areas where clearer indicator frameworks and better measurement tools are needed to ensure social and institutional dimensions are fully captured.

- Physical risk management remains a high-confidence domain.

Indicators related to Water Quality, Flood Vulnerability, and Data Quality achieved the highest average scores in both relevance and confidence. These are often supported by direct monitoring, sensor data, and visible outcomes, making them easier to assess. For users, this reinforces the reliability of physical resilience indicators, while also underscoring the importance of pairing them with institutional and behavioral metrics for a complete picture.

- Timespan and uncertainty shape decision-making value.

Incorporating operational timespan and confidence scores adds critical nuance to resilience assessments. For instance, SG solution recorded a relatively short Timespan of three years and moderate confidence across key indicators—such as institutional coordination and environmental monitoring. Despite addressing high-relevance categories like system performance and flood regulation, SG's resilience score (3.73) reflects uncertainties tied to early-stage technological deployment and limited longitudinal data. This guide illustrates how such results should be interpreted not as limitations, but as signals for careful

monitoring, iterative learning, and support. Short-term solutions with moderate confidence may evolve into long-term assets with appropriate investment and refinement.

- SRM and resilience enhance strategic planning, not just evaluation.

When applied iteratively, the SRM and the resilience assessment framework go beyond static evaluation—they actively support forward-looking planning. Together, they help projects define performance targets, anticipate monitoring and data needs, identify system interdependencies, and plan for scalability and long-term sustainability. By integrating both tools throughout the project lifecycle—from proposal development and implementation to ex-post learning—teams can better align solutions with contextual risks, capacity gaps, and impact potential. This guide demonstrates their combined use as dynamic instruments for not just an assessment tool but a planning and design guide.

Taken together, this report provides a step-by-step pathway for using SRM in diverse contexts. It demonstrates how structured, participatory, and context-sensitive methods can reveal not just which solutions perform well, but why—and under what conditions. As a guide, it equips users to customize the SRM, foster local engagement, and use resilience scoring as a strategic tool for adaptation planning, governance improvement, and long-term impact.

5.2 Recommendations

The recommendations synthesize key insights from the ex-post assessment process and adopt a forward-looking lens to support the refinement of the SRM, strengthen future resilience assessments, and enhance the practical integration of results into adaptation planning and project development. They are structured across four thematic domains:

Indicator co-definition and implementation:

- Prioritize early alignment between indicators and data availability. Co-defining indicators with stakeholders was effective in increasing relevance and local buy-in, but several demonstrators struggled with low confidence due to insufficient or delayed data. Future planning should embed data infrastructure and reporting mechanisms from the outset.
- Balance sector-specific and systemic indicators. Solutions often emphasized physical infrastructure or digital tools but lacked strong metrics on cross-cutting aspects like governance, coordination, and long-term viability. Expanding systemic indicators can reveal important enablers or barriers beyond technical effectiveness.

Assessment process and governance

- Invest in institutional continuity and handover. Some solutions faced risks of reduced resilience post-project due to lack of institutional anchoring. Future project design should ensure that key institutional partners are not only involved but empowered to continue monitoring, learning, and adapting.
- Acknowledge uncertainty transparently. Performance gaps were often driven not by failure but by early implementation stages or incomplete data. Rather than masking this uncertainty, the resilience should continue to treat confidence scores and timespan estimates as tools to communicate risks and inform adaptive management.

Guidance for application and scaling

- Use SRM and resilience assessment as a learning and targeting tool. Rather than ranking or scoring for comparison, the method proved most valuable in identifying strengths, gaps, and areas for reinforcement. Future projects should apply them at multiple stages—design, mid-term, and post-implementation—for iterative learning.

- Promote scalability through replicable formats. The SRM enabled structured application across varied contexts. By maintaining and expanding replicable formats—such as indicator libraries, scoring templates, and visual summaries—future projects can adopt the method efficiently, ensuring comparability, and supporting broader integration of resilience thinking into adaptation planning.

Methodological refinements

- Improve integration with sustainability profiles. While D5.2 assessed environmental, social, and economic sustainability, and this deliverable focused on resilience, future work should formally link these frameworks. Incorporating Timespan into the resilience capacity formula would strengthen comparability. Solutions scoring high across both dimensions may serve as strong candidates for replication, offering models that are not only effective and scalable but also enduring.
- Advance indicator standardization for underrepresented domains. Categories like Governance and Policy or Liveability and Comfort were rarely applied, often due to vague definitions or missing metrics. Targeted development of standard indicators and benchmarks in these domains is recommended.

These recommendations extend beyond future TransformAr iterations, offering guidance to any climate adaptation initiative aiming to connect solution performance with systemic resilience. This report itself serves as a practical guide for conducting ex-post assessments in both sustainability (D5.9) and resilience—providing tested methods, structured tools, and real-world applications. It emphasizes the value of combining systematic scoring approaches, such as the SRM, with inclusive stakeholder engagement to ensure context-sensitive insights. By doing so, resilience assessment becomes more than a measurement exercise; it supports governance innovation, strategic foresight, cross-sector dialogue, and adaptive learning. Embedding resilience thinking early in project design helps clarify trade-offs, guide investment decisions, and align solutions with long-term transformation pathways. Ultimately, resilience evaluation should serve as a strategic enabler of sustainable adaptation.

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ANNEX: SCORES

FOR RESILIENCE ASSESSMENT IN EACH DEMONSTRATOR

Lappeenranta, Finland

AAS*	Performance categories	Indicator	Sub-indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Weighting	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence
URB	Flood vulnerability	Reduced Flood Hazard		5,0	8 %	5,0	0,42
URB		Reduced Runoff		5,0	8 %	5,0	0,42
URB		Reduced Peak Flow		5,0	8 %	5,0	0,42
URB		Reduction in Flood Damage		5,0	8 %	5,0	0,42
URB	Water Quality	Reduction in Nutrients	Reduction in Nitrogen Loading	5,0	8 %	5,0	0,42
URB		Reduction in Metals	Reduction in Copper Loading	5,0	8 %	5,0	0,42
URB	Management and Coordination	Internal Communication and Collaboration		5,0	8 %	5,0	0,42
URB		Institutional Coordination		5,0	8 %	5,0	0,42
URB		Commitment Fulfillment		4,0	7 %	5,0	0,34
URB	Financial Viability	Maintenance	Cost	5,0	8 %	4,0	0,34
URB	Risk and Resilience	Ice Mitigation Strategy		5,0	8 %	4,0	0,34
URB		Snowmelt Overflow Prevention		5,0	8 %	4,0	0,34
SWMM	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Data Usability Satisfaction		4,0	9 %	5,0	0,45
SWMM	System Performance	System Uptime		4,0	9 %	5,0	0,45
SWMM		Sensor Provider Match		3,0	7 %	3,0	0,20
SWMM	Data Quality	Data Accuracy		4,0	9 %	3,0	0,27
SWMM	Financial Viability	Maintenance	Maintenance cost	5,0	11 %	3,0	0,34
SWMM		Business Model Economic Risk		3,0	19 %	4,0	0,75
SWMM	Risk and Resilience	Sensor Coverage Redundancy		4,0	25 %	4,0	1,00
CAF	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Usability Satisfaction		5,0	15 %	5,0	0,74
CAF		App Utilization	App Utilization Rate	4,0	12 %	4,0	0,47
CAF	Management and Coordination	Engagement strategy		5,0	15 %	4,0	0,59
CAF	Financial Viability	Investment	Investment cost	5,0	15 %	5,0	0,74
CAF		Maintenance	Maintenance cost	5,0	15 %	5,0	0,74
CAF		Operation	Operational cost	5,0	15 %	5,0	0,74
CAF	Risk and Resilience	Partner Dependency		5,0	15 %	5,0	0,74

* Nature-based urban stormwater solution (URB), Stormwater Monitoring (SWMM) and Citizen App Finland™ (CAF)

Westcountry Region, UK

AAS*	Performance category	Indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Weighting	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence
ICW	Readiness and Feasibility	Methods Applied	5,0	5 %	3,0	0,15
ICW	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Meeting	3,0	3 %	4,0	0,12
ICW		Workshop	3,0	3 %	4,0	0,12
ICW		Event	3,0	3 %	4,0	0,12
ICW		Feedback	3,0	3 %	4,0	0,12
ICW		Local Landowners Engaging	5,0	5 %	4,0	0,19
ICW		Flood Vulnerability	Water Retention Capacity	4,0	4 %	4,0
ICW	Water Quality	Reduction in Nitrogen Loading	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,24
ICW		Reduction in Phosphorus Loading	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,24
ICW		Improvement in pH level	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,24
ICW		Improvement in dissolved oxygen level	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,24
ICW	Environmental Impact	Climate	3,0	3 %	5,0	0,15
ICW		Water	4,0	4 %	4,0	0,16
ICW		Land Use Change	3,0	3 %	3,0	0,09
ICW	Biodiversity and Habitat	Increase in species richness	2,0	2 %	4,0	0,08
ICW	Livability and Comfort	Community Resilience	2,0	2 %	2,0	0,04
ICW	Management and Coordination	Communication Strategy Readiness	1,0	1 %	5,0	0,05
ICW		Stakeholder Coordination	4,0	4 %	2,0	0,08
ICW		Internal Communication and Collaboration	4,0	4 %	5,0	0,19
ICW		Commitment	5,0	5 %	3,0	0,15
ICW	Financial Viability	Investment	5,0	5 %	4,0	0,19
ICW		Maintenance	5,0	5 %	4,0	0,19
ICW	Risk and Resilience	Landowner Maintenance Willingness	4,0	4 %	3,0	0,12
ICW		Phosphate Credit Calculation Change	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,24
ICW		Local Authority Permission	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,24
ICW		Sediment Management	5,0	5 %	4,0	0,19

* Integrated Constructed Wetlands (ICW)

AAS*	Performance category	Indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Weighting	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence	
ICWM	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Private Investment Attracted	3,0	3 %	2,0	0,05	
ICWM		Citizen Science Engagement	3,0	3 %	5,0	0,14	
ICWM		Training	2,0	2 %	5,0	0,09	
ICWM		CSI Community Resilience	2,0	2 %	5,0	0,09	
ICWM	System Performance	System Uptime	5,0	5 %	3,0	0,14	
ICWM		System Scalability	4,0	4 %	3,0	0,11	
ICWM		Integration Capability	4,0	4 %	3,0	0,11	
ICWM		Installation Requirements	5,0	5 %	4,0	0,18	
ICWM		User Customization Options	4,0	4 %	2,0	0,07	
ICWM		Response Efficiency	5,0	5 %	3,0	0,14	
ICWM		Sensor Lifespan	3,0	3 %	2,0	0,05	
ICWM		Tech-enabled Monitoring	2,0	2 %	2,0	0,04	
ICWM		Sensor Provider Match	3,0	3 %	4,0	0,11	
ICWM		Computing Power	4,0	4 %	5,0	0,18	
ICWM		Sensor Maintenance Frequency	4,0	4 %	3,0	0,11	
ICWM		Software Update Frequency	4,0	4 %	3,0	0,11	
ICWM		Data Quality	Continuous monitoring	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,23
ICWM			Sampling Validation	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,23
ICWM	Monitoring Data Accuracy		5,0	5 %	5,0	0,23	
ICWM	Sampling Data Matching		5,0	5 %	5,0	0,23	
ICWM	Sensor Coverage Redundancy		3,0	3 %	3,0	0,08	
ICWM	Management and Coordination	Citizen Science Program	2,0	2 %	5,0	0,09	
ICWM		Stakeholder Coordination	3,0	3 %	5,0	0,14	
ICWM		Monitoring Spot Accessibility	4,0	4 %	5,0	0,18	
ICWM	Financial Viability	Investment	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,23	
ICWM		Maintenance	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,23	
ICWM		Operational	5,0	5 %	5,0	0,23	
ICWM		Business Model Economic Risk	3,0	3 %	3,0	0,08	
ICWM	Risk and Resilience	Cloud Data Capacity and Storage	2,0	2 %	5,0	0,09	
ICWM		Partner Dependency	1,0	1 %	3,0	0,03	

* Integrated Constructed Wetlands Monitoring (ICWM)

AAS*	Performance category	Indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Weighting	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence
GB	Readiness and Feasibility	Phosphate Credit Implementation Readiness	4,0	6 %	4,0	0,24
GB		Policy Interventions	4,0	6 %	2,0	0,12
GB	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Event Participation	3,0	4 %	4,0	0,18
GB		Private Sector Investment Engagement	5,0	7 %	5,0	0,37
GB	Governance and Policy	Flexible Financing Models	3,0	4 %	3,0	0,13
GB	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Legal Mechanism Effectiveness	4,0	6 %	4,0	0,24
GB		Ethical Brokerage Coordination	4,0	6 %	5,0	0,29
GB		Credit Revenue Generation	4,0	6 %	3,0	0,18
GB		Payment Realization	5,0	7 %	4,0	0,29
GB		Landowner Satisfaction	4,0	6 %	3,5	0,21
GB		Investor Satisfaction	4,0	6 %	3,5	0,21
GB		Ethical Broker Satisfaction	2,0	3 %	5,0	0,15
GB	Management and Coordination	Stakeholder Communication and Collaboration	4,0	6 %	5,0	0,29
GB	Financial Viability	Setup	3,0	4 %	4,0	0,18
GB		Operational	3,0	4 %	4,0	0,18
GB	Risk and Resilience	Conservation Covenant	4,0	6 %	5,0	0,29
GB		Credit Calculation Impact	4,0	6 %	3,0	0,18
GB		Market Demand Uncertainties	4,0	6 %	3,5	0,21

* Green bonds (GB)

Galicia, Spain

AAS	Performance categories	Indicator	Sub-indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Weighting	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence	
RI	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Stakeholders Participation		4,0	10 %	4,0	0,41	
RI	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Decision Tool Perception Improvement		5,0	13 %	5,0	0,64	
RI		Stakeholder Collaboration Impact		4,0	10 %	5,0	0,51	
RI		Decision-Making Tool Perception		4,0	10 %	5,0	0,51	
RI		Resilience Enhancement Actions and Roadmap		3,0	8 %	4,0	0,31	
RI		Stakeholder Groups Diversity		3,0	8 %	5,0	0,38	
RI		Management and Coordination	Institutional Coordination		5,0	13 %	3,0	0,38
RI	Financial Viability	Investment	Design and Data Resources	3,0	8 %	3,0	0,23	
RI			Investment cost efficiency	4,0	10 %	4,0	0,41	
MRM	Data Quality	Continuous monitoring		5,0	8 %	5,0	0,40	
MRM		Data Accuracy	Data Accuracy Rate	4,0	6 %	3,0	0,19	
MRM			Data Accuracy Satisfaction	5,0	8 %	4,0	0,32	
MRM	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Environmental Data Access		4,0	6 %	3,5	0,23	
MRM		Stakeholder Use of Data		4,0	6 %	4,0	0,26	
MRM		Data Satisfaction		4,0	6 %	4,0	0,26	
MRM		Traditional Knowledge Integration		5,0	8 %	4,0	0,32	
MRM	Management and Coordination	Stakeholder Coordination		5,0	8 %	5,0	0,40	
MRM	Financial Viability	Maintenance	Maintenance cost	3,0	5 %	5,0	0,24	
MRM	Risk and Resilience	Environmental Challenges		4,0	6 %	2,5	0,16	
MRM	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Shellfish Sector Publications/Outputs		4,0	6 %	4,0	0,26	
MRM		Risks and Adaptation Awareness Increase		5,0	8 %	4,0	0,32	
MRM		Population that enhance resilience		5,0	8 %	4,0	0,32	
MRM		Actors involved in the adaptive process		5,0	8 %	5,0	0,40	
INTERM	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Topography Area	Topography Area Rate	2,0	4 %	4,0	0,14	
INTERM			Topography Area Satisfaction	2,0	4 %	4,0	0,14	
INTERM		Submerged Bathymetry Area	Spatial Resolution Rate	3,0	5 %	4,0	0,21	
INTERM			Spatial Resolution Satisfaction	2,0	4 %	4,0	0,14	
INTERM		Spatial Resolution		1,0	2 %	4,0	0,07	
INTERM		Current Flow and Turbidity		3,0	5 %	4,0	0,21	
INTERM		Sandbank Monitoring Completion		4,0	7 %	4,0	0,28	
INTERM		Sampling Requierments	Sampling Requierments Rate	4,0	7 %	4,0	0,28	
INTERM			Sampling Requierments Satisfaction	4,0	7 %	4,0	0,28	
INTERM		Data Quality	Sampling Validation		4,0	7 %	4,0	0,28
INTERM		Management and Coordination	Strategy Scheme Readiness		4,0	7 %	4,0	0,28
INTERM			Stakeholder Involvement and Collaboration		5,0	9 %	4,0	0,35
INTERM	Financial Viability	Investment	Investment cost	3,0	5 %	3,0	0,16	
INTERM			Morphodynamic Modelling	4,0	7 %	1,0	0,07	
INTERM		Investment cost efficiency	4,0	7 %	3,0	0,21		
INTERM		Business Model Economic Risk		4,0	7 %	3,0	0,21	
INTERM	Risk and Resilience	Partner Dependency		4,0	7 %	4,0	0,28	

* Resilience Index (RI), Mussel-Raft Monitoring (MRM), Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM)

Oristano, Italy

AAS*	Performance categories	Indicator	Sub-indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Weighting	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence
COAST	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Meeting	Meeting attendance	2,0	5 %	5,0	0,25
COAST	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Public Authorities Engagement	-	5,0	13 %	3,0	0,38
COAST		Observatory Reporting	-	4,0	10 %	5,0	0,50
COAST		Private Sector Engagement	-	4,0	10 %	2,0	0,20
COAST		Contract Action	Contract Action Achievement	5,0	13 %	3,0	0,38
COAST		Management and Coordination	Stakeholder Coordination	-	5,0	13 %	3,0
COAST	Commitment Fulfillment		-	5,0	13 %	2,0	0,25
COAST	Financial Viability	Investment	Setup Cost	5,0	13 %	5,0	0,63
COAST	Risk and Resilience	Political and Policy Stability	-	5,0	13 %	3,0	0,38
SG	System Performance	System Scalability	-	4,0	11 %	3,5	0,38
SG		Tech-enabled Monitoring	Use of Energy	5,0	14 %	5,0	0,68
SG		Sensor Maintenance Frequency	-	4,0	11 %	4,0	0,43
SG	Data Quality	Continuous monitoring	-	5,0	14 %	3,0	0,41
SG		Data Collection and Analysis	-	5,0	14 %	3,0	0,41
SG	Management and Coordination	Institutional Coordination	-	4,0	11 %	2,0	0,22
SG	Financial Viability	Maintenance	Maintenance cost	5,0	14 %	5,0	0,68
SG		Operation	Operational cost	5,0	14 %	4,0	0,54

* Coastal Contracts (COAST), Smart Gates (SG)

Guadeloupe, France

AAS*	Performance categories	Indicator	Sub-indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Weighting	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence
NUDG	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Commitment Fulfillment	-	5,0	38 %	1,0	0,38
NUDG		Behavioral Change	Shower Duration Improvement	3,0	23 %	3,0	0,69
NUDG		Water Consumption	Change in Water Consumption	2,0	15 %	2,0	0,31
NUDG		Energy Use	Change in Energy Use	2,0	15 %	2,0	0,31
NUDG	Management and Coordination	Timely Support Response	-	1,0	8 %	4,0	0,31
AF	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Organization Conversion	Public Organization	5,0	18 %	4,0	0,71
AF		Private Sector Engagement	-	5,0	18 %	2,0	0,36
AF	Governance and Policy	Governance Structure	Governance Structure Flexibility	4,0	14 %	4,0	0,57
AF	Management and Coordination	Commitment Fulfillment	-	4,0	14 %	3,0	0,43
AF	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Public-Private Project Alignment	-	5,0	18 %	4,0	0,71
AF	Risk and Resilience	Fund Financing Viability	-	5,0	18 %	3,0	0,54

* Nudging (NUDG), Adaptation Fund (AF)

Egaleo, Greece

AAS*	Performance categories	Indicator	Sub-indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Weighting	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence
AWAR	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Meeting	Meeting Attendance	5,0	7 %	5,0	0,35
AWAR			Meeting Engagement Satisfaction	4,0	6 %	3,0	0,17
AWAR		Workshop	Workshop Attendance	5,0	7 %	4,0	0,28
AWAR			Workshop Participation Satisfaction	3,0	4 %	4,0	0,17
AWAR		Event Attendance	Event Attendance Rate	4,0	6 %	4,0	0,22
AWAR			Event Attendance Satisfaction	3,0	4 %	2,0	0,08
AWAR		Training	Training Participation	5,0	7 %	5,0	0,35
AWAR			Training Participation Satisfaction	4,0	6 %	2,0	0,11
AWAR	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Educational Material Design	-	3,0	4 %	3,0	0,13
AWAR		Awareness-raising Modules	-	3,0	4 %	4,0	0,17
AWAR		Innovation in Youth Engagement	-	5,0	7 %	5,0	0,35
AWAR		Implementation Effectiveness Satisfaction	-	3,0	4 %	3,0	0,13
AWAR	Management and Coordination	Stakeholder Coordination	-	2,0	3 %	2,0	0,06
AWAR		Teacher Engagement	-	4,0	6 %	4,0	0,22
AWAR	Financial Viability	Investment	Investment cost	1,0	1 %	1,0	0,01
AWAR	Investment cost efficiency		5,0	7 %	5,0	0,35	
AWAR	Risk and Resilience	Partner Dependency	-	1,0	1 %	2,0	0,03
AWAR		Sustained Engagement	-	3,0	4 %	3,0	0,13
AWAR		Data Accessibility	-	5,0	7 %	5,0	0,35
AWAR		Awareness-Behavior Gap	-	4,0	6 %	4,0	0,22
CAE	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Survey	Survey Participation	1,0	2 %	1,0	0,02
CAE			Survey Effectiveness Satisfaction	2,0	4 %	2,0	0,08
CAE		Meeting	Meeting Attendance	5,0	10 %	5,0	0,50
CAE			Meeting Engagement Satisfaction	3,0	6 %	2,0	0,12
CAE	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Usability Satisfaction	-	4,0	8 %	5,0	0,40
CAE		App Utilization	App Utilization Rate	5,0	10 %	5,0	0,50
CAE			App Utilization Satisfaction	4,0	8 %	1,0	0,08
CAE		Financial Viability	Maintenance	Maintenance cost	3,0	6 %	3,0
CAE	Maintenance cost efficiency			5,0	10 %	5,0	0,50
CAE	Operation		Operational cost	4,0	8 %	5,0	0,40
CAE			Operational cost efficiency	4,0	8 %	5,0	0,40
CAE	Risk and Resilience	Local Control and Ownership	-	5,0	10 %	5,0	0,50
CAE		Data Hosting and Accessibility	-	5,0	10 %	5,0	0,50

* Awareness-raising Modules (AWAR), Citizen App Egaleo (CAE)

AAS*	Performance categories	Indicator	Sub-indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence
CIH	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Workshop	Workshop Attendance	5,0	5,0	0,50
CIH			Workshop Participation Satisfaction	4,0	5,0	0,40
CIH		Event Attendance	Event Attendance Rate	5,0	5,0	0,50
CIH			Event Attendance Satisfaction	4,0	2,0	0,16
CIH		Training	Training Participation	5,0	5,0	0,50
CIH			Training Participation Satisfaction	3,0	2,0	0,12
CIH		Feedback	Feedback Submission	3,0	2,0	0,12
CIH			Feedback Submission Satisfaction	5,0	5,0	0,50
CIH	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Behavioral Change	Behavioral Change Satisfaction	5,0	5,0	0,50
CIH	Management and Coordination	Stakeholder Collaboration	-	5,0	4,0	0,40
CIH	Risk and Resilience	Political and Administrative Support	-	2,0	1,0	0,04
CIH		Local Needs and Values	-	4,0	3,0	0,24
DSI	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Mortality rate	-	4,0	5,0	0,54
DSI		Health impacts of air pollution	-	5,0	5,0	0,68
DSI		Data Reliability	-	5,0	5,0	0,68
DSI		Potential in Decision-Making	-	3,0	3,0	0,24
DSI	Financial Viability	Investment	Analysis Resources	4,0	4,0	0,43
DSI			Investment cost efficiency	3,0	4,0	0,32
DSI	Risk and Resilience	Unpredictable Climate Impacts	-	5,0	1,0	0,14
DSI		Engagement and Cooperation	-	5,0	5,0	0,68
DSI		Organizational Perception	-	3,0	3,0	0,24

* Climate Innovation Hub (CIH), Demand Analysis for Social Services /Infrastructure (DSI)

AAS*	Performance categories	Indicator	Sub-indicator	Relevance (1-5)	Weighting	Confidence (1-5)	Weight Confidence
SCS	System Performance	System Uptime	System Uptime Rate	5,0	7 %	5,0	0,36
SCS			System Uptime Satisfaction	4,0	6 %	5,0	0,29
SCS		System Scalability	-	3,0	4 %	4,0	0,17
SCS		System Response	Response Efficiency Rate	5,0	7 %	5,0	0,36
SCS			Response Efficiency Satisfaction	5,0	7 %	5,0	0,36
SCS		Sensor Lifespan	Sensor Lifespan Rate	5,0	7 %	4,0	0,29
SCS			Sensor Lifespan Satisfaction	3,0	4 %	3,0	0,13
SCS		Tech-enabled Monitoring	Use of Energy	1,0	1 %	5,0	0,07
SCS		Computing Power	-	1,0	1 %	5,0	0,07
SCS		Sensor Maintenance Frequency	-	3,0	4 %	3,0	0,13
SCS		Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Coverage Area	Coverage Area Rate	5,0	7 %	5,0
SCS	Coverage Area Efficiency			5,0	7 %	5,0	0,36
SCS	Data Quality	Data Accuracy	Data Accuracy Rate	5,0	7 %	5,0	0,36
SCS			Data Accuracy Satisfaction	5,0	7 %	5,0	0,36
SCS	Financial Viability	Investment	Investment cost efficiency	4,0	6 %	5,0	0,29
SCS		Maintenance	Maintenance cost	2,0	3 %	5,0	0,14
SCS			Maintenance cost efficiency	2,0	3 %	4,0	0,12
SCS		Operation	Operational cost	1,0	1 %	5,0	0,07
SCS	Operational cost efficiency		2,0	3 %	4,0	0,12	
SCS	Risk and Resilience	Resource Allocation	-	3,0	4 %	5,0	0,22

* Smart Climate Stations (SCS)

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.